

Microbial Mediated Tolerance: reproducible meta-analysis and summary of literature review

Tronson & Enders:[Ecology] Root microbes can improve plant tolerance to insect damage: A systematic

2024-08-07

Load R packages needed for analysis and data visualizations

```
library(metafor)
```

```
## Loading required package: Matrix
```

```
## Loading required package: metadat
```

```
## Loading required package: numDeriv
```

```
##
```

```
## Loading the 'metafor' package (version 4.4-0). For an  
## introduction to the package please type: help(metafor)
```

```
library(tidyverse) #includes ggplot, tidyr, dplyr
```

```
## -- Attaching core tidyverse packages ----- tidyverse 2.0.0 --
```

```
## v dplyr      1.1.4      v readr      2.1.5
```

```
## v forcats   1.0.0      v stringr    1.5.1
```

```
## v ggplot2   3.4.4      v tibble     3.2.1
```

```
## v lubridate 1.9.3      v tidyr      1.3.1
```

```
## v purrr     1.0.2
```

```
## -- Conflicts ----- tidyverse_conflicts() --
```

```
## x tidyr::expand() masks Matrix::expand()
```

```
## x dplyr::filter() masks stats::filter()
```

```
## x dplyr::lag()    masks stats::lag()
```

```
## x tidyr::pack()  masks Matrix::pack()
```

```
## x tidyr::unpack() masks Matrix::unpack()
```

```
## i Use the conflicted package (<http://conflicted.r-lib.org/>) to force all conflicts to become errors
```

```
library(stringr)
```

```
library(ggpubr)
```

```
library(metaviz) #for fancy forest plots
```

```
library(tidytext) #for more logical layout of x axes within hedges' d figure (via reorder_within)
```

```
library(reshape2) #for melting mostly
```

```
##
## Attaching package: 'reshape2'
##
## The following object is masked from 'package:tidyr':
##
##   smiths
```

```
library(scales) #for pretty labels via label_wrap()
```

```
##
## Attaching package: 'scales'
##
## The following object is masked from 'package:purrr':
##
##   discard
##
## The following object is masked from 'package:readr':
##
##   col_factor
```

```
library(devtools)
```

```
## Loading required package: usethis
```

```
library(ggmosaic) #don't think I actually ended up using this; ggplot2 facets were prettier/less fussy
library(remotes)
```

```
##
## Attaching package: 'remotes'
##
## The following objects are masked from 'package:devtools':
##
##   dev_package_deps, install_bioc, install_bitbucket, install_cran,
##   install_deps, install_dev, install_git, install_github,
##   install_gitlab, install_local, install_svn, install_url,
##   install_version, update_packages
##
## The following object is masked from 'package:usethis':
##
##   git_credentials
```

```
#install_github("gastonstat/colortools")
library(colortools) #for harmonious color palettes used in mosaic plot building
```

Before we get into biomass effect sizes, let's summarize who considered biomass vs. other measures of tolerance. This helps us determine what data we have to use for the meta-analysis. Data file = "tolerance lit review table_working1august.csv"

```
toltab <- read.csv(file = "tolerance lit review table_working1august.csv")

grouped.toltab <- toltab %>% group_by(Citation)
tallied.toltab <- grouped.toltab %>% tally() #number of entries per citation
nrow(grouped.toltab %>% tally()) #number of papers = 40
```

```
## [1] 40
```

```
uni.tolcat <- grouped.tolcat %>% summarise(biom = Biomass == "None",  
                                           phot = Photosynthesis == "None",  
                                           oxid = Oxidative.stress == "None") %>%  
unique()
```

```
## Warning: Returning more (or less) than 1 row per 'summarise()' group was deprecated in  
## dplyr 1.1.0.
```

```
## i Please use 'reframe()' instead.
```

```
## i When switching from 'summarise()' to 'reframe()', remember that 'reframe()'
```

```
## always returns an ungrouped data frame and adjust accordingly.
```

```
## Call 'lifecycle::last_lifecycle_warnings()' to see where this warning was
```

```
## generated.
```

```
## 'summarise()' has grouped output by 'Citation'. You can override using the
```

```
## '.groups' argument.
```

```
summary(uni.tolcat) #where FALSE = this category was considered
```

```
## Citation      biom      phot      oxid  
## Length:41     Mode :logical Mode :logical Mode :logical  
## Class :character FALSE:41    FALSE:5     FALSE:7  
## Mode :character TRUE :36    TRUE :34
```

```
uni.tolcat$biom <- as.integer(as.logical(uni.tolcat$biom)) #convert true/false to 1/0  
uni.tolcat$phot <- as.integer(as.logical(uni.tolcat$phot))  
uni.tolcat$oxid <- as.integer(as.logical(uni.tolcat$oxid))
```

```
melted.tolcat <- melt(uni.tolcat)
```

```
## Using Citation as id variables
```

```
melted.tolcat$year <- as.integer(gsub(".*\\s", "", melted.tolcat$Citation))  
melted.tolcat$Citation <- reorder(melted.tolcat$Citation, melted.tolcat$year)
```

```
uni.tolcat.plot <- ggplot(melted.tolcat, aes(variable, Citation)) +  
  geom_tile(color = "black", fill = "white", size = .6) +  
  geom_point(aes(color = factor(value)), size = 1.8) +  
  scale_color_manual(values = c("black", "white"),  
                    labels = c("Examined", "Unexamined")) +  
  coord_equal(expand = 0) +  
  theme_bw() + coord_fixed() +  
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1, size = 10),  
        legend.key = element_rect(color = "black", fill = "white")) +  
  scale_x_discrete(labels = c("biom" = "Biomass",  
                             "phot" = "Photosynthesis",  
                             "oxid" = "Oxidative stress")) +  
  labs(x = element_blank(), y = element_blank(), color = element_blank())
```

```
## Warning: Using 'size' aesthetic for lines was deprecated in ggplot2 3.4.0.
## i Please use 'linewidth' instead.
## This warning is displayed once every 8 hours.
## Call 'lifecycle::last_lifecycle_warnings()' to see where this warning was
## generated.
```

```
## Coordinate system already present. Adding new coordinate system, which will
## replace the existing one.
```

```
uni.tolcat.plot
```



```
# setwd("[CHOOSE YOUR WD]")
# ggsave(uni.tolcat.plot, filename = "unique.tolcat.by.paper.pdf")
```

Load meta-analysis data Data file = "hedge-d-simple-ContinMod.csv"

```
d.data <- read.csv(file = "hedge-d-simple-ContinMod_R.csv")
#what papers are in the systematic review but missing from the meta-analysis?
setdiff(melted.tolcat$Citation, d.data$Citation) #should be 5
```

```
## [1] "Borowicz 1997" "Gan et al. 2017"
## [3] "Kabaluk and Ericsson 2007" "Metwally et al. 2022"
## [5] "Real-Santillán et al. 2019"
```

```
#what papers are in the meta-analysis but missing from the systematic review?  
setdiff(d.data$Citation, melted.tolcat$Citation) #should be 0
```

```
## character(0)
```

Calculating effect sizes: We're going with a comparison of the two +herbivore treatments (+/- microbe).

These generally fall into: aboveground biomass, belowground biomass, total (vegetative) biomass, and reproductive biomass.

```
es.all <- escalc(measure = "SMD",  
               m1i = InMi.Mean, sd1i = InMi.SD, n1i = InMi.N,  
               m2i = PlusIn.Mean, sd2i = PlusIn.SD, n2i = PlusIn.N,  
               data = d.data)  
  
es.repro <- es.all[es.all$ES.Category == "Reproductive",]  
es.shoot <- es.all[es.all$ES.Category == "Shoot",]  
es.root <- es.all[es.all$ES.Category == "Root",]  
es.total <- es.all[es.all$ES.Category == "Total",]
```

However, our three effect sizes of interest—aboveground biomass, belowground biomass, total biomass, and reproductive biomass—almost certainly covary. Let's confirm.

```
#root biomass:shoot biomass: clear positive correlation  
scatter.rs <- merge(data.frame(es.root$yi, es.root$Rep.Name),  
                  data.frame(es.shoot$yi, es.shoot$Rep.Name),  
                  by.x = "es.root.Rep.Name", by.y = "es.shoot.Rep.Name")  
ggplot(data = scatter.rs, aes(x = es.shoot.yi, y = es.root.yi)) +  
  geom_point() + stat_cor(method = "pearson")
```


#root biomass:reproductive biomass: few points, but negative correlation?

```
scatter.rp <- merge(data.frame(es.root$yi, es.root$Rep.Name),
  data.frame(es.repro$yi, es.repro$Rep.Name),
  by.x = "es.root.Rep.Name", by.y = "es.repro.Rep.Name")
ggplot(data = scatter.rp, aes(x = es.repro.yi, y = es.root.yi)) +
  geom_point() + stat_cor(method = "pearson")
```



```
#shoot biomass:reproductive biomass: few points, but negative correlation?
scatter.sp <- merge(data.frame(es.shoot$yi, es.shoot$Rep.Name),
  data.frame(es.repro$yi, es.repro$Rep.Name),
  by.x = "es.shoot.Rep.Name", by.y = "es.repro.Rep.Name")
ggplot(data = scatter.sp, aes(x = es.repro.yi, y = es.shoot.yi)) +
  geom_point() + stat_cor(method = "pearson")
```


Well, this means we probably have to do composite effect sizes...

To aggregate effect sizes without assuming independence (as would be the case if `struct = "ID"` was specified), we need to estimate ρ , the average pairwise correlation between estimates.

```
#calculate effect sizes
es.all <- escalc(measure = "SMD",
                m1i = InMi.Mean, sd1i = InMi.SD, n1i = InMi.N,
                m2i = PlusIn.Mean, sd2i = PlusIn.SD, n2i = PlusIn.N,
                data = d.data)

#output counts of observations from each tolerance category for all (before aggregation/composite effect sizes)
es.all %>% count (TolCat, sort = TRUE)
```

```
##
##           TolCat  n
## 1           No effect 83
## 2 Constitutive overcompensation 23
## 3      Uncategorized tolerance  8
## 4           Induced compensation  6
## 5           Susceptibility  6
## 6 Constitutive compensation  5
## 7 Constitutive susceptibility  4
## 8           Compensation  3
## 9 Induced overcompensation  3
## 10          Overcompensation  3
## 11 Induced susceptibility  2
```

```

## 12      Partial compensation  2
## 13 Induced partial compensation  1

#find average pairwise correlation
#simplify dataframe to enable pivoting
es.trim <- select(es.all, c("Citation", "Rep.Name", "Exp", "ES.Category", "yi", "vi"))
es.pivot <- pivot_wider(es.trim, names_from = ES.Category, values_from = c(yi, vi))

#calculate the correlation between pairwise comparisons of sampling errors among ES.Category levels
es.cor <- data.frame(es.pivot$Rep.Name, es.pivot$vi_Reproductive, es.pivot$vi_Root, es.pivot$vi_Shoot,
r.s <- cor((es.pivot$vi_Shoot/es.pivot$yi_Shoot),
           (es.pivot$vi_Root/es.pivot$yi_Root),
           use = "pairwise.complete.obs")
t.s <- cor((es.pivot$vi_Shoot/es.pivot$yi_Shoot),
           (es.pivot$vi_Total/es.pivot$yi_Total),
           use = "pairwise.complete.obs")
p.s <- cor((es.pivot$vi_Shoot/es.pivot$yi_Shoot),
           (es.pivot$vi_Reproductive/es.pivot$yi_Reproductive),
           use = "pairwise.complete.obs")
t.r <- cor((es.pivot$vi_Root/es.pivot$yi_Root),
           (es.pivot$vi_Total/es.pivot$yi_Total),
           use = "pairwise.complete.obs")
p.r <- cor((es.pivot$vi_Root/es.pivot$yi_Root),
           (es.pivot$vi_Reproductive/es.pivot$yi_Reproductive),
           use = "pairwise.complete.obs")
r.t <- cor((es.pivot$vi_Total/es.pivot$yi_Total),
           (es.pivot$vi_Reproductive/es.pivot$yi_Reproductive),
           use = "pairwise.complete.obs")

#a couple don't exist, which makes sense; some of these were rarer than others and total encompasses ro
#get the mean of all non-NA rho
my.rho <- mean(c(p.r, p.s, r.s))

#oof finally, let's get composite effect sizes to use for our meta-analysis
es.agg <- aggregate.escalc(es.all, cluster = Rep.Name, rho = my.rho)

demo1 <- select(es.all, c("Citation", "Rep.Name", "Exp", "ES.Category", "yi", "vi"))
demo2 <- select(es.agg, c("Citation", "Rep.Name", "Exp", "ES.Category", "yi", "vi"))

#output summary stats (mean, median, SD, SE, range) for hedges d in each tolerance category, make sure
source("group_by_summary_stats.R")

group_by_summary_stats(es.all, yi, TolCat) #all data points before aggregation/composite effect sizes

## # A tibble: 13 x 7
##   TolCat
##   <chr>
## 1 Compensation
## 2 Constitutive compensation
## 3 Constitutive overcompensation
## 4 Constitutive susceptibility
## 5 Induced compensation
## 6 Induced overcompensation

```

	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE	Range
1 Compensation	3	9.16	8.09	2.02	1.17	7.9-11.49
2 Constitutive compensation	5	1.55	1.11	1.21	0.540	0.61-3.56
3 Constitutive overcompensation	23	4.33	3.42	4.64	0.967	0.57-22.17
4 Constitutive susceptibility	4	-1.39	-1.41	0.29	0.143	-1.71--1.01
5 Induced compensation	6	0.83	0.78	0.39	0.159	0.44-1.48
6 Induced overcompensation	3	1.3	1.34	0.08	0.0449	1.21-1.34

```
## 7 Induced partial compensation      1  1.71  1.71 NA    NA      1.71-1.71
## 8 Induced susceptibility            2 -0.74 -0.74 0.08  0.0555 -0.79--0.68
## 9 No effect                        83  0.19  0.13 0.9   0.0985 -1.94-3.87
## 10 Overcompensation                3 12.0  14.8 8.24  4.76   2.65-18.36
## 11 Partial compensation             2  6.34  6.34 1.34  0.948  5.39-7.29
## 12 Susceptibility                  6 -1.72 -1.23 1.52  0.622  -4.76--0.71
## 13 Uncategorized tolerance          8  1.5   1.39 0.41  0.146  1.28-2.51
```

```
group_by_summary_stats(es.agg, yi, PlFuGu, Plant..Family.)#using aggregated dataset with composite effe
```

```
## 'summarise()' has grouped output by 'PlFuGu'. You can override using the
## '.groups' argument.
```

```
## # A tibble: 43 x 8
## # Groups:   PlFuGu [2]
##   PlFuGu      Plant..Family.      N Mean Median    SD      SE Range
##   <chr>      <chr>          <int> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <chr>
## 1 Cultivated "Arachis hypogaea\nPeanut\~ 3  1.19  1.2  0.52  0.298  0.67~
## 2 Cultivated "Capsicum annuum \nSweet p~ 4  1.31  1.35  5.03  2.52  -4.7~
## 3 Cultivated "Capsicum chinense\nHabane~ 1  0.44  0.44 NA    NA    0.44~
## 4 Cultivated "Cucumis sativus\nCucumber~ 1  1.72  1.72 NA    NA    1.72~
## 5 Cultivated "Cucurbita pepo\nZucchini\~ 1 -0.05 -0.05 NA    NA    -0.0~
## 6 Cultivated "Fragaria x ananassa\nStra~ 4  0.38  0.33  0.53  0.266  -0.1~
## 7 Cultivated "Glycine max\nSoybean\n(Fa~ 7  0.05  0.26  0.54  0.203  -0.7~
## 8 Cultivated "Medicago sativa\nAlfalfa\~ 1  2.72  2.72 NA    NA    2.72~
## 9 Cultivated "Oryza sativa\nRice\n(Poac~ 12 0.7   0.68  0.34  0.0970 0.12~
## 10 Cultivated "Saccharum spp. hybrid\nSu~ 1  1.02  1.02 NA    NA    1.02~
## # i 33 more rows
```

```
#now examine differences between host plant derived tolerance and microbial-derived tolerance using the
```

```
es.all %>% count (Effect.Herbivory, sort = TRUE)
```

```
##
##   Effect.Herbivory  n
## 1          None 54
## 2           Neg 48
## 3       Unknown 44
## 4           Pos  3
```

```
group_by_summary_stats(es.all, yi, TolCat,Effect.Herbivory)
```

```
## 'summarise()' has grouped output by 'TolCat'. You can override using the
## '.groups' argument.
```

```
## # A tibble: 21 x 8
## # Groups:   TolCat [13]
##   TolCat      Effect.Herbivory      N Mean Median    SD      SE Range
##   <chr>      <chr>          <int> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <chr>
## 1 Compensation      Neg          3  9.16  8.09  2.02  1.17  7.9--
## 2 Constitutive compens~ Neg          5  1.55  1.11  1.21  0.540 0.61~
```

```
## 3 Constitutive overcom~ Neg          7  7.51  5.34  7.39  2.79  1.17~
## 4 Constitutive overcom~ None        15  2.95  3.4   1.77  0.456 0.57~
## 5 Constitutive overcom~ Pos         1  2.72  2.72 NA    NA    2.72~
## 6 Constitutive suscept~ Neg         2 -1.2  -1.2  0.26  0.185 -1.3~
## 7 Constitutive suscept~ None        2 -1.57 -1.57 0.19  0.136 -1.7~
## 8 Induced compensation Neg          6  0.83  0.78  0.39  0.159 0.44~
## 9 Induced overcompensa~ None        2  1.28  1.28  0.1   0.0682 1.21~
## 10 Induced overcompensa~ Pos        1  1.34  1.34 NA    NA    1.34~
## # i 11 more rows
```

```
all.effectherb <-group_by_summary_stats(es.all, yi, TolCat,Effect.Herbivory)
```

```
## 'summarise()' has grouped output by 'TolCat'. You can override using the
## '.groups' argument.
```

```
agg.effectherb <-group_by_summary_stats(es.agg, yi, TolCat,Effect.Herbivory)
```

```
## 'summarise()' has grouped output by 'TolCat'. You can override using the
## '.groups' argument.
```

Doing composite effect sizes means we kinda disconnect from the tolerance categories. Let's at least try to visualize how they associate with effect sizes.

```
#can plot all values (es.all) or aggregated (es.agg)
tolcat.figure <- ggplot(es.all, aes(x = TolCat, y = yi, shape = ES.Category)) +
  annotate(geom = "rect", xmin = .6, xmax = 1.4,
    ymin = min(es.all$yi-1), ymax = max(es.all$yi)+1,
    fill = "lavender", alpha = .3) +
  annotate(geom = "rect", xmin = 1.6, xmax = 4.4,
    ymin = min(es.all$yi-1), ymax = max(es.all$yi)+1,
    fill = "#D0FACE", alpha = .3) +
  annotate(geom = "rect", xmin = 4.6, xmax = 7.4,
    ymin = min(es.all$yi-1), ymax = max(es.all$yi)+1,
    fill = "#f1fbef", alpha = .5) +
  annotate(geom = "rect", xmin = 7.6, xmax = 10.4,
    ymin = min(es.all$yi-1), ymax = max(es.all$yi)+1,
    fill = "#F4E6C9", alpha = .3) +
  annotate(geom = "rect", xmin = 10.6, xmax = 11.4,
    ymin = min(es.all$yi-1), ymax = max(es.all$yi)+1,
    fill = "lightgray", alpha = .3) +
  annotate(geom = "rect", xmin = 11.6, xmax = 14.4,
    ymin = min(es.all$yi-1), ymax = max(es.all$yi)+1,
    fill = "#f1d2d2", alpha = .3) +
  geom_jitter(width = .2, height = 0, size = 1.75) + theme_bw() +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1, vjust = 1),
    #legend.position = c(.903,.67),
    #legend.background = element_rect(fill = "#fcfaf9"),
    legend.direction = "horizontal",
    legend.position = "top",
    aspect.ratio = .3) +
  scale_color_manual(values = c("#4c1e4f", "#b5a886", "#3083dc", "#f44174")) +
  scale_x_discrete(limits = c("Uncategorized tolerance",
```

```

      "Constitutive overcompensation",
      "Induced overcompensation", "Overcompensation",
      "Constitutive compensation",
      "Induced compensation", "Compensation",
      "Constitutive partial compensation",
      "Induced partial compensation",
      "Partial compensation", "No effect",
      "Constitutive susceptibility",
      "Induced susceptibility", "Susceptibility"),
  labels = label_wrap(22)) +
  scale_shape_manual(values = c(8, 6, 2, 5)) +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 0, linetype = "dashed") +
  labs(x = element_blank(), y = expression(paste("Hedges' ", italic("d"))),
       title = element_blank(), color = element_blank(), shape = element_blank())
tolcat.figure

```



```

#can also plot which observations show host plant derived tolerance and microbial-mediated tolerance
tolcat.figure.effectherb <- ggplot(es.all, aes(x = TolCat, y = yi, shape = Effect.Herbivory)) +
  annotate(geom = "rect", xmin = .6, xmax = 1.4,
         ymin = min(es.all$yi-1), ymax = max(es.all$yi)+1,
         fill = "lavender", alpha = .3) +
  annotate(geom = "rect", xmin = 1.6, xmax = 4.4,
         ymin = min(es.all$yi-1), ymax = max(es.all$yi)+1,
         fill = "#DOFACE", alpha = .3) +

```

```

annotate(geom = "rect", xmin = 4.6, xmax = 7.4,
  ymin = min(es.all$yi-1), ymax = max(es.all$yi)+1,
  fill = "#f1fbef", alpha = .5) +
annotate(geom = "rect", xmin = 7.6, xmax = 10.4,
  ymin = min(es.all$yi-1), ymax = max(es.all$yi)+1,
  fill = "#F4E6C9", alpha = .3) +
annotate(geom = "rect", xmin = 10.6, xmax = 11.4,
  ymin = min(es.all$yi-1), ymax = max(es.all$yi)+1,
  fill = "lightgray", alpha = .3) +
annotate(geom = "rect", xmin = 11.6, xmax = 14.4,
  ymin = min(es.all$yi-1), ymax = max(es.all$yi)+1,
  fill = "#f1d2d2", alpha = .3) +
geom_jitter(width = .2, height = 0, size = 1.75) + theme_bw() +
theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1, vjust = 1),
  #legend.position = c(.903,.67),
  #legend.background = element_rect(fill = "#fcfaf9"),
  legend.direction = "horizontal",
  legend.position = "top",
  aspect.ratio = .3) +
scale_color_manual(values = c("#4c1e4f", "#b5a886", "#3083dc", "#f44174")) +
scale_x_discrete(limits = c("Uncategorized tolerance",
  "Constitutive overcompensation",
  "Induced overcompensation", "Overcompensation",
  "Constitutive compensation",
  "Induced compensation", "Compensation",
  "Constitutive partial compensation",
  "Induced partial compensation",
  "Partial compensation", "No effect",
  "Constitutive susceptibility",
  "Induced susceptibility", "Susceptibility"),
  labels = label_wrap(22)) +
scale_shape_manual(values = c(6, 8, 2, 5)) +
geom_hline(yintercept = 0, linetype = "dashed") +
labs(x = element_blank(), y = expression(paste("Hedges' ", italic("d"))),
  title = element_blank(), color = element_blank(), shape = element_blank())

```

tolcat.figure.effectherb


```
#plot tolerance categories with counts across Effect of Herbivory (neg, pos, none, unknown)
```

```
#reorder TolCats first for better plotting
```

```
es.all$TolCat <- ordered(es.all$TolCat, levels = c("Uncategorized tolerance",
  "Constitutive overcompensation",
  "Induced overcompensation", "Overcompensation",
  "Constitutive compensation",
  "Induced compensation", "Compensation",
  "Constitutive partial compensation",
  "Induced partial compensation",
  "Partial compensation", "No effect",
  "Constitutive susceptibility",
  "Induced susceptibility", "Susceptibility"))
```

```
tolcat.barchart.effectherb <- ggplot(es.all, aes(x=Effect.Herbivory, fill = TolCat)) +
  geom_bar() +
  geom_text(aes (label = after_stat(count)), stat = "count", position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5)) +
  scale_x_discrete(limits = c("Unknown", "Neg", "None", "Pos")) +
  theme_bw() +
  scale_fill_manual(values = c("lavender", "darkgreen", "green3", "green2", "lightgreen", "#D0FACE", "#f1f1f1"),
  labs(title = "Tolerance Categories by Herbivory Effect - all effect size data")
```

```
tolcat.barchart.effectherb
```

Tolerance Categories by Herbivory Effect – all effect size data


```
#setwd("/Users/emilytronson/OneDrive - purdue.edu/Tronson Meeting Files/Literature Review")
#ggsave(filename = "ToleranceCatFigure.pdf", plot = tolcat.figure)
```

Let's model!

Meta-Regression using dataset with composite effect sizes and multiple moderators

```
main.model <- rma.mv(yi, vi, random = ~ 1 | Citation/Exp/Rep.Name,
                    data = es.agg)
summary(main.model)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 113; method: REML)
##
##   logLik   Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -229.1777  458.3553  466.3553  477.2293  466.7291
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed      factor
## sigma^2.1 0.8156 0.9031   35    no      Citation
## sigma^2.2 1.9482 1.3958   72    no      Citation/Exp
## sigma^2.3 0.3096 0.5564  113    no      Citation/Exp/Rep.Name
##
## Test for Heterogeneity:
```

```
## Q(df = 112) = 744.7397, p-val < .0001
##
## Model Results:
##
## estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## 0.9906 0.2560 3.8701 0.0001 0.4889 1.4924 ***
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
#Number of papers: 35
#Number of independent experiments: 72
#Number of comparisons/effect sizes: 119
#Q = 811
#Grand mean effect size: 1.1406 [0.5248, 1.7565]
```

Code for calculating I^2 from https://www.metafor-project.org/doku.php/tips:i2_multilevel_multivariate.

```
W <- diag(1/main.model$vi)
X <- model.matrix(main.model)
P <- W - W %*% X %*% solve(t(X) %*% W %*% X) %*% t(X) %*% W
100 * sum(main.model$sigma2) / (sum(main.model$sigma2) + (main.model$k-main.model$p)/sum(diag(P)))
```

```
## [1] 94.50817
```

```
#I2 = 95.4%
```

```
100 * main.model$sigma2 / (sum(main.model$sigma2) + (main.model$k-main.model$p)/sum(diag(P)))
```

```
## [1] 25.081076 59.908002 9.519087
```

```
#39.8% of I2 is between-cluster (Citation) heterogeneity, and 55.6% is within-cluster (Experiment) het
```

```
xtabs(~TolCat, data = es.agg)
```

```
## TolCat
##           Compensation      Constitutive compensation
##           3                2
## Constitutive overcompensation  Constitutive susceptibility
##           18                3
##           Induced compensation  Induced partial compensation
##           3                  1
##           No effect             Overcompensation
##           67                   3
##           Partial compensation  Susceptibility
##           2                    6
##           Uncategorized tolerance
##           5
```

Meta-analysis MODERATORS Let's weave in moderators. This large model unfortunately drops a lot of observations with missing data, so we won't really use it. Instead, we'll use a meta-regression approach.

```
es.agg.na <- es.agg
es.agg.na[es.agg.na=="Unknown"] <- NA
mods.model <- rma.mv(yi, vi, random = ~ 1|Citation/Exp/Rep.Name,
                    mods = ~InFeGu + RoShHe + InFit + PlFuGu +
                        RegrowthPeriod + MiFuGu + MiSource + CoCoSimple + Environ,
                    data = es.agg.na)
```

```
## Warning: 47 rows with NAs omitted from model fitting.
```

```
mods.model
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 66; method: REML)
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim      sqrt  nlvls  fixed      factor
## sigma^2.1  0.0000  0.0000    21    no      Citation
## sigma^2.2  3.0200  1.7378    48    no      Citation/Exp
## sigma^2.3  0.0000  0.0001    66    no      Citation/Exp/Rep.Name
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 39) = 255.7140, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:27):
## QM(df = 26) = 55.3931, p-val = 0.0007
##
## Model Results:
##
##              estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb
## intrcpt              9.5546  2.7240   3.5076  0.0005   4.2158
## InFeGuMixed herbivore community  -7.2278  2.4882  -2.9048  0.0037  -12.1047
## InFeGuOther              1.4609  2.0162   0.7246  0.4687   -2.4908
## InFeGuPiercing-sucking    0.8428  1.8612   0.4528  0.6507   -2.8052
## RoShHeRoot             -0.6552  0.5821  -1.1255  0.2604   -1.7962
## RoShHeShoot            -1.0860  0.5775  -1.8806  0.0600   -2.2178
## InFitNegative           1.3498  1.6828   0.8021  0.4225   -1.9483
## InFitNo effect           0.4343  1.8232   0.2382  0.8117   -3.1391
## InFitPositive            0.1350  1.8269   0.0739  0.9411   -3.4457
## PlFuGuUncultivated        5.2689  2.0333   2.5913  0.0096    1.2838
## RegrowthPeriodYes       -5.7075  2.2369  -2.5515  0.0107  -10.0918
## MiFuGuEndophytic entomopathogen  1.2002  1.6039   0.7483  0.4543   -1.9433
## MiFuGuMixed             -1.2662  0.7670  -1.6508  0.0988   -2.7696
## MiFuGuN-fixing          -0.0377  0.5902  -0.0638  0.9491   -1.1944
## MiFuGuOther PGPF        -2.0023  1.3368  -1.4979  0.1342   -4.6223
## MiFuGuPGPB              -4.4276  3.3332  -1.3283  0.1841  -10.9606
## MiSourceCommercial      -1.6994  2.5449  -0.6678  0.5043   -6.6873
## MiSourceField isolate   -0.4749  2.2620  -0.2099  0.8337   -4.9084
## MiSourceLab stock        7.4469  3.3348   2.2331  0.0255    0.9109
## MiSourceMixed            0.9341  2.3557   0.3965  0.6917   -3.6829
```

```

## CoCoSimpleSingle          -1.4615  1.8769  -0.7786  0.4362  -5.1402
## CoCoSimpleSmall consortia -0.1749  1.8489  -0.0946  0.9246  -3.7986
## EnvironExperimental station -0.0114  1.2363  -0.0092  0.9927  -2.4345
## EnvironField             -0.2345  1.8384  -0.1275  0.8985  -3.8376
## EnvironGreenhouse        -7.0894  2.6485  -2.6767  0.0074  -12.2804
## EnvironGrowth chamber    -5.9680  3.2199  -1.8535  0.0638  -12.2788
## EnvironOther field       -7.5799  2.4649  -3.0751  0.0021  -12.4110
##                               ci.ub
## intrcpt                   14.8935  ***
## InFeGuMixed herbivore community -2.3510  **
## InFeGuOther                5.4125
## InFeGuPiercing-sucking     4.4908
## RoShHeRoot                 0.4858
## RoShHeShoot                0.0458  .
## InFitNegative              4.6480
## InFitNo effect             4.0077
## InFitPositive              3.7157
## PlFuGuUncultivated         9.2540  **
## RegrowthPeriodYes         -1.3233  *
## MiFuGuEndophytic entomopathogen 4.3437
## MiFuGuMixed                0.2371  .
## MiFuGuN-fixing            1.1191
## MiFuGuOther PGPF          0.6177
## MiFuGuPGPB                2.1054
## MiSourceCommercial         3.2884
## MiSourceField isolate     3.9586
## MiSourceLab stock         13.9830  *
## MiSourceMixed             5.5511
## CoCoSimpleSingle          2.2173
## CoCoSimpleSmall consortia  3.4489
## EnvironExperimental station  2.4118
## EnvironField              3.3687
## EnvironGreenhouse         -1.8984  **
## EnvironGrowth chamber     0.3429  .
## EnvironOther field       -2.7487  **
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

Now for separate models for separate moderators, accomplished through a kind and detailed tutorials on the metafor page (using the predict function). The creator of this package mentions that this is poor practice, but that when dealing with missing data, doing otherwise can bring issues of its own. Our 119 observations were cut to 72 in the model above because of missing data (i.e., only 72 observations had no missing information for one or more moderators). Therefore, I'm going with the one-by-one analysis. The biggest drawback to keep in mind with this seems to be that it ignores how moderators covary.

```

#change "Other" (capturing Hessian fly paper) to "Galling"
es.agg[es.agg$InFeGu=="Other",]$InFeGu <- "Galling"
es.agg[es.agg$InFeGu=="Mixed herbivore community",]$InFeGu <- "Mixed community"

#create model with a single moderator: insect feeding guild
IFG.mod <- rma.mv(yi, vi, random = ~1|Citation/Exp/Rep.Name, mods = ~InFeGu,
                 data = es.agg)
IFG.mod #omnibus test says NS (p = 0.49)

```

```

##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 113; method: REML)
##
## Variance Components:
##
##          estim      sqrt  nlvls  fixed          factor
## sigma^2.1  1.1236  1.0600    35     no           Citation
## sigma^2.2  1.8695  1.3673    72     no           Citation/Exp
## sigma^2.3  0.3188  0.5646   113     no  Citation/Exp/Rep.Name
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 109) = 739.7192, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:4):
## QM(df = 3) = 2.4290, p-val = 0.4883
##
## Model Results:
##
##          estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt          1.3461  0.3589   3.7503  0.0002   0.6426  2.0496 ***
## InFeGuGalling    -1.2397  1.5200  -0.8155  0.4148  -4.2189  1.7396
## InFeGuMixed community  -0.9476  0.6677  -1.4191  0.1559  -2.2563  0.3612
## InFeGuPiercing-sucking -0.3658  0.7855  -0.4657  0.6414  -1.9053  1.1737
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```

#the intercept gives us the estimated (average) effect size associated with the alphabetically first mod
#to find the estimates for the other levels, we must...

```

```

ifg.predict <- as.data.frame(predict(IFG.mod, newmods = rbind(c(0,0,0), c(1,0,0), c(0,1,0), c(0,0,1))))
ifg.predict$level <- sort(unique(es.agg$InFeGu))
ifg.predict$n <- 0
for (i in 1:length(ifg.predict$level)) {
  ifg.predict$n[i] <- nrow(es.agg[which(es.agg$InFeGu == ifg.predict$level[i]),])
} #tally up the number of effect sizes representing each level of the moderator
ifg.predict$pval <- IFG.mod$QMp
ifg.predict$QM <- IFG.mod$QM
ifg.predict$moderator <- "Herbivore feeding guild"

```

```

#change "Mixed" (non-descript) to "Whole plant"
es.agg[es.agg$RoShHe=="Mixed",]$RoShHe <- "Whole plant"

```

```

#create model with a single moderator: root or shoot herbivory
RSH.mod <- rma.mv(yi, vi, random = ~1|Citation/Exp/Rep.Name, mods = ~RoShHe,
  data = es.agg)
RSH.mod #omnibus test says NS (p = 0.63)

```

```

##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 113; method: REML)
##
## Variance Components:
##
##          estim      sqrt  nlvls  fixed          factor

```

```

## sigma^2.1  0.9458  0.9725    35    no          Citation
## sigma^2.2  1.8758  1.3696    72    no          Citation/Exp
## sigma^2.3  0.3578  0.5982   113    no  Citation/Exp/Rep.Name
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 110) = 717.8132, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):
## QM(df = 2) = 0.3045, p-val = 0.8588
##
## Model Results:
##
##              estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt              0.9907  0.5248   1.8878  0.0591  -0.0379  2.0193
## RoShHeShoot          0.1091  0.5846   0.1866  0.8520  -1.0368  1.2550
## RoShHeWhole plant  -0.1898  0.6483  -0.2929  0.7696  -1.4604  1.0807
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

*#the intercept gives us the estimated (average) effect size associated with the alphabetically first mo
#to find the estimates for the other levels, we must...*

```

rsh.predict <- as.data.frame(predict(RSH.mod, newmods = rbind(c(0,0), c(1,0), c(0,1))))
rsh.predict$level <- sort(unique(es.agg$RoShHe))
rsh.predict$n <- 0
for (i in 1:length(rsh.predict$level)) {
  rsh.predict$n[i] <- nrow(es.agg[which(es.agg$RoShHe == rsh.predict$level[i]),])
} #tally up the number of effect sizes representing each level of the moderator
rsh.predict$pval <- RSH.mod$QMp
rsh.predict$QM <- RSH.mod$QM
rsh.predict$moderator <- "Site of herbivore feeding"

```

```

#remove unknowns
es.agg.IF <- es.agg[-which(es.agg$InFit=="Unknown"),]
es.agg.IF <- es.agg.IF[-which(es.agg.IF$InFit=="Mixed"),] #had to drop "Mixed" as it was represented by

#create model with a single moderator: insect fitness
IF.mod <- rma.mv(yi, vi, random = ~1|Citation/Exp/Rep.Name, mods = ~InFit,
                data = es.agg.IF)
IF.mod #omnibus test says p < 0.0001

```

```

##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 79; method: REML)
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim      sqrt  nlvls  fixed      factor
## sigma^2.1  0.7117  0.8436   28    no          Citation
## sigma^2.2  1.9845  1.4087   56    no          Citation/Exp
## sigma^2.3  0.0000  0.0000   79    no  Citation/Exp/Rep.Name
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:

```

```

## QE(df = 76) = 482.9618, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):
## QM(df = 2) = 20.5415, p-val < .0001
##
## Model Results:
##
##           estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt          1.5022  0.4071   3.6901  0.0002   0.7043   2.3001 ***
## InFitNo effect   -0.4636  0.4177  -1.1100  0.2670  -1.2823   0.3550
## InFitPositive    -1.3805  0.4526  -3.0501  0.0023  -2.2677  -0.4934 **
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

*#the intercept gives us the estimated (average) effect size associated with the alphabetically first moderator
#to find the estimates for the other levels, we must...*

```

if.predict <- as.data.frame(predict(IF.mod, newmods = rbind(c(0,0), c(1,0), c(0,1))))
if.predict$level <- sort(unique(es.agg.IF$InFit))
if.predict$n <- 0
for (i in 1:length(if.predict$level)) {
  if.predict$n[i] <- nrow(es.agg.IF[which(es.agg.IF$InFit == if.predict$level[i]),])
} #tally up the number of effect sizes representing each level of the moderator
if.predict$pval <- IF.mod$QMp
if.predict$QM <- IF.mod$QM
if.predict$moderator <- "Effect of microbe(s) on herbivore fitness"

```

*#remove unknowns
#endophytic entomopathogens are represented by less than 5 observations; let's lump them in with other moderators*

```

es.agg.MFG <- es.agg[-which(es.agg$MiFuGu=="Unknown"),]
es.agg.MFG$MiFuGu[es.agg.MFG$MiFuGu=="Endophytic entomopathogen"] <- "Other PGPB"
#rename "PGPB" to "Other PGPB" since N-fixing bacteria are kinda PGPB
es.agg.MFG[es.agg.MFG$MiFuGu == "PGPB",]$MiFuGu <- "Other PGPB"
#relatedly, specify N-fixing bacteria
es.agg.MFG[es.agg.MFG$MiFuGu == "N-fixing",]$MiFuGu <- "N-fixing bacteria"

```

```

#create model with a single moderator
MFG.mod <- rma.mv(yi, vi, random = ~1|Citation/Exp/Rep.Name, mods = ~MiFuGu,
                 data = es.agg.MFG)
MFG.mod #omnibus test says significant (p < 0.001)

```

```

##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 107; method: REML)
##
## Variance Components:
##
##           estim      sqrt  nlvls  fixed      factor
## sigma^2.1  0.9217  0.9601    34    no      Citation
## sigma^2.2  2.1876  1.4790    71    no      Citation/Exp
## sigma^2.3  0.1530  0.3912   107    no      Citation/Exp/Rep.Name
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 102) = 629.3392, p-val < .0001

```

```
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:5):
## QM(df = 4) = 19.7598, p-val = 0.0006
##
## Model Results:
##
##              estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt           0.8635  0.3188   2.7085  0.0068   0.2386  1.4883  **
## MiFuGuMixed       -0.0629  0.4335  -0.1450  0.8847  -0.9126  0.7869
## MiFuGuN-fixing bacteria -0.0933  0.5542  -0.1683  0.8663  -1.1796  0.9930
## MiFuGuOther PGPB    1.7449  0.5483   3.1821  0.0015   0.6701  2.8196  **
## MiFuGuOther PGPF    0.0220  0.5745   0.0383  0.9695  -1.1040  1.1480
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

*#the intercept gives us the estimated (average) effect size associated with the alphabetically first mo
#to find the estimates for the other levels, we must...*

```
mfg.predict <- as.data.frame(predict(MFG.mod,
                                   newmods = rbind(c(0,0,0,0), c(1,0,0,0),
                                                  c(0,1,0,0), c(0,0,1,0),
                                                  c(0,0,0,1))))
mfg.predict$level <- sort(unique(es.agg.MFG$MiFuGu))
mfg.predict$n <- 0
for (i in 1:length(mfg.predict$level)) {
  mfg.predict$n[i] <- nrow(es.agg.MFG[which(es.agg.MFG$MiFuGu == mfg.predict$level[i]),])
} #tally up the number of effect sizes representing each level of the moderator
mfg.predict$pval <- MFG.mod$QMp
mfg.predict$QM <- MFG.mod$QM
mfg.predict$moderator <- "Microbial inoculant functional guild"
```

```
#create model with a single moderator: root or shoot herbivory
PFG.mod <- rma.mv(yi, vi, random = ~1|Citation/Exp/Rep.Name, mods = ~P1FuGu,
                 data = es.agg)
PFG.mod #omnibus test says NS (p = 0.90)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 113; method: REML)
##
## Variance Components:
##
##           estim      sqrt  nlvls  fixed      factor
## sigma^2.1 0.9238  0.9611    35    no      Citation
## sigma^2.2 1.9500  1.3964    72    no      Citation/Exp
## sigma^2.3 0.3119  0.5585   113    no  Citation/Exp/Rep.Name
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 111) = 723.3967, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficient 2):
## QM(df = 1) = 0.0001, p-val = 0.9932
##
```

```
## Model Results:
##
##              estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt              1.0059  0.3224   3.1205  0.0018   0.3741  1.6378  **
## PlFuGuUncultivated  -0.0048  0.5575  -0.0085  0.9932  -1.0975  1.0880
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
PFG.predict <- as.data.frame(predict(PFG.mod, newmods = rbind(c(0), c(1))))
PFG.predict$level <- sort(unique(es.agg$PlFuGu))
PFG.predict$n <- 0
for (i in 1:length(PFG.predict$level)) {
  PFG.predict$n[i] <- nrow(es.agg[which(es.agg$PlFuGu == PFG.predict$level[i]),])
} #tally up the number of effect sizes representing each level of the moderator
PFG.predict$pval <- PFG.mod$QMp
PFG.predict$QM <- PFG.mod$QM
PFG.predict$moderator <- "Plant cultivation status"
```

```
es.agg.RP <- es.agg[-which(es.agg$RegrowthPeriod=="Unknown"),]
es.agg.RP$RegrowthPeriodDuration_inDays <- as.numeric(es.agg.RP$RegrowthPeriodDuration_inDays)
#create model with a single moderator: root or shoot herbivory
RP.mod <- rma.mv(yi, vi, random = ~1|Citation/Exp/Rep.Name, mods = ~RegrowthPeriodDuration_inDays,
                data = es.agg.RP)
RP.mod #omnibus test says NS (p = 0.40)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 111; method: REML)
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim      sqrt  nlvls  fixed      factor
## sigma^2.1  0.9318  0.9653   34    no      Citation
## sigma^2.2  1.9059  1.3805   70    no      Citation/Exp
## sigma^2.3  0.3092  0.5560  111    no      Citation/Exp/Rep.Name
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 109) = 699.5745, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficient 2):
## QM(df = 1) = 0.0824, p-val = 0.7741
##
## Model Results:
##
##              estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb
## intrcpt              1.0063  0.2916   3.4514  0.0006   0.4348
## RegrowthPeriodDuration_inDays -0.0039  0.0137  -0.2870  0.7741  -0.0307
##
##              ci.ub
## intrcpt              1.5777  ***
## RegrowthPeriodDuration_inDays 0.0229
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

##		Citation	Rep.Name	Exp	Study
## 1		Tao et al. 2016	Ac-High	57	156.00000
## 2		Cosme et al. 2016	Adult-Larval-RWW	40	122.50000
## 3		Cosme et al. 2016	Adult-RWW	40	120.50000
## 4		Kula et al. 2005	Ag	16	40.00000
## 5		Tao et al. 2016	Ai-High	62	161.00000
## 6		Tao et al. 2016	Al-High	58	157.00000
## 7	Zitlалpopoca-Hernandez et al.	2017	AMF	1	3.50000
## 8		Tao et al. 2016	Ap-High	60	159.00000
## 9		Tao et al. 2016	As-High	59	158.00000
## 10	Bennett and Bever	2007	At	70	175.00000
## 11		Tao et al. 2016	Av-High	61	160.00000
## 12	Charters et al.	2022	Avalon	13	74.50000
## 13		Raglin et al. 2022	b73-Ba-Sterilized	51	139.00000
## 14		Raglin et al. 2022	b73-Ba-Unsterilized	51	140.00000
## 15		Raglin et al. 2022	b73-Unsterilized	51	141.00000
## 16	Zitlалpopoca-Hernandez et al.	2017	Bb	1	2.50000
## 17	Zitlалpopoca-Hernandez et al.	2017	Bb-AMF	1	4.50000
## 18	Batool et al.	2022	Bb-SoilDrench-2018	29	61.00000
## 19	Batool et al.	2022	Bb-SoilDrench-2019	30	67.00000
## 20	Batool et al.	2022	Bb-Ta-SoilDrench-2018	29	65.00000
## 21	Batool et al.	2022	Bb-Ta-SoilDrench-2019	30	71.00000
## 22		Kula et al. 2005	Be	20	44.00000
## 23		Coy et al. 2019	Bermudagrass	42	126.00000
## 24	Charters et al.	2022	Cadenza	14	75.50000
## 25		Yang et al. 2021	Caterpillar-Con	71	181.00000
## 26		Yang et al. 2021	Caterpillar-Hetero	71	183.00000
## 27		Yang et al. 2021	Caterpillar-NFCon	71	182.00000
## 29	Bernaola and Stout	2019	Crowley-1	32	92.00000
## 30	Bernaola and Stout	2019	Crowley-2	33	93.00000
## 31	Balog et al.	2017	cvLongChili	25	56.00000
## 32	Prischmann-Voldseth et al.	2020	cvMoll-Ab	8	15.00000
## 33	Prischmann-Voldseth et al.	2020	cvMoll-Ab-Ri	8	17.00000
## 34	Prischmann-Voldseth et al.	2020	cvMoll-Ri	8	16.00000
## 35	Prischmann-Voldseth et al.	2020	cvNewt-Ab	7	12.00000
## 36	Prischmann-Voldseth et al.	2020	cvNewt-Ab-Ri	7	14.00000
## 37	Prischmann-Voldseth et al.	2020	cvNewt-Ri	7	13.00000
## 38	Whyle et al.	2022	cvSeascape	64	166.00000
## 39	Balog et al.	2017	cvSweetBanana	28	59.00000
## 40	Balog et al.	2017	cvSweetBell	26	57.00000
## 41	Balog et al.	2017	cvSweetFlexum	27	58.00000
## 42	Whyle et al.	2022	cvTribute	65	167.00000
## 43	Whyle et al.	2022	cvWasatch	66	168.00000
## 44		Kula et al. 2005	Ec	18	42.00000
## 45	Bernaola and Stout	2021	Exp-1	2	70.33333
## 46	Bernaola and Stout	2021	Exp-2	3	71.33333
## 47	Bernaola and Stout	2021	Exp-3	4	72.33333
## 48	Bernaola and Stout	2021	Exp-4	5	73.33333
## 49		Coy et al. 2019	Fescue	41	125.00000
## 50		Currie et al. 2011	Gf	10	20.50000

## 51	Currie et al.	2011	Gf-Gm	10	22.50000
## 52	Brunner et al.	2014	GHouse-Bj	72	184.00000
## 53	Brunner et al.	2014	GHouse-Bj-Ab	72	186.00000
## 54	Brunner et al.	2014	GHouse-Bj-Da	72	185.00000
## 55	Selvaraj et al.	2020	Gi	69	171.00000
## 56	Selvaraj et al.	2020	Gi-Rspp	69	173.00000
## 57	Bennett and Bever	2007	Glomus	70	174.00000
## 58	Bennett and Bever	2007	Glomus-At-Sc	70	177.00000
## 59	Currie et al.	2011	Gm	10	21.50000
## 60	Gange et al.	2002	Jacobea	50	138.00000
## 61	Cosme et al.	2016	Larval-LWW	40	121.50000
## 62	Kula et al.	2005	Lc	21	45.00000
## 63	Bernaola and Stout	2019	Mamou-1	34	94.00000
## 64	Bernaola and Stout	2019	Mamou-2	35	95.00000
## 65	Raglin et al.	2022	oh43-Ba-Sterilized	52	142.00000
## 66	Raglin et al.	2022	oh43-Ba-Unsterilized	52	143.00000
## 67	Raglin et al.	2022	oh43-Unsterilized	52	144.00000
## 68	Raglin et al.	2022	pa91-Ba-Sterilized	53	145.00000
## 69	Raglin et al.	2022	pa91-Ba-Unsterilized	53	146.00000
## 70	Raglin et al.	2022	pa91-Unsterilized	53	147.00000
## 71	He et al.	2017	Peanut-Fm	11	25.00000
## 72	He et al.	2017	Peanut-Gv	11	27.00000
## 73	He et al.	2017	Peanut-Ri	11	26.00000
## 74	Raglin et al.	2022	phg84-Ba-Sterilized	54	148.00000
## 75	Raglin et al.	2022	phg84-Ba-Unsterilized	54	149.00000
## 76	Raglin et al.	2022	phg84-Unsterilized	54	150.00000
## 77	Raglin et al.	2022	phj40-Ba-Sterilized	55	151.00000
## 78	Raglin et al.	2022	phj40-Ba-Unsterilized	55	152.00000
## 79	Raglin et al.	2022	phj40-Unsterilized	55	153.00000
## 80	Gange et al.	2002	Plantago	49	137.00000
## 81	Kula et al.	2005	Ps	19	43.00000
## 82	Zeng et al.	2022	Rep-1	6	11.00000
## 83	Wang et al.	2022	Rep-10	63	162.00000
## 84	de Bobadilla et al.	2017	Rep-11	67	169.00000
## 85	Orians et al.	2017	Rep-2	9	18.00000
## 86	Borowicz	2009	Rep-3	36	108.50000
## 87	Caccavo et al.	2022	Rep-4	37	110.00000
## 88	Chen et al.	2021	Rep-5	38	115.50000
## 89	Contreras-Cornejo et al.	2021	Rep-6	39	117.50000
## 90	Forlano et al.	2022	Rep-7	47	134.00000
## 91	Frew et al.	2020	Rep-8	48	135.50000
## 92	Rivera-Vega et al.	2022	Rep-9	56	154.50000
## 93	Kula et al.	2005	Rh	22	46.00000
## 94	Eichholtzer et al.	2021	Ri-High	68	170.00000
## 95	Selvaraj et al.	2020	Rspp	69	172.00000
## 96	Kula et al.	2005	Sa	23	47.00000
## 97	Dabré et al.	2021	Saint-Simone-Ri-Bj	46	131.00000
## 98	Dabré et al.	2021	Saint-Simone-Ri-Bj-Bp	46	132.00000
## 100	Charters et al.	2022	Skyfall	15	76.50000
## 101	Kula et al.	2005	Sn	17	41.00000
## 102	Batool et al.	2022	Ta-SoilDrench-2018	29	63.00000
## 103	Batool et al.	2022	Ta-SoilDrench-2019	30	69.00000
## 104	He et al.	2017	Tomato-Fm	12	28.00000
## 105	He et al.	2017	Tomato-Gv	12	30.00000

## 106		He et al. 2017	Tomato-Ri	12	29.00000
## 107		Coy et al. 2020	Trial-1	43	127.00000
## 108		Coy et al. 2020	Trial-2	44	128.00000
## 109		Dabré et al. 2021	Varennnes-Ri-Bj	45	129.00000
## 110		Dabré et al. 2021	Varennnes-Ri-Bj-Bp	45	130.00000
## 111		Yang et al. 2021	Weevil-Con	71	178.00000
## 112		Yang et al. 2021	Weevil-Hetero	71	180.00000
## 113		Yang et al. 2021	Weevil-NFCon	71	179.00000
##	MultiComp	Full.Treatment.Rep	Effect.Herbivory		TolCat
## 1	No	No	Unknown		Susceptibility
## 2	Yes	Yes	Neg		Induced compensation
## 3	Yes	Yes	None		No effect
## 4	No	Yes	None	Constitutive	overcompensation
## 5	No	No	Unknown		Susceptibility
## 6	No	No	Unknown		No effect
## 7	Yes	Yes	None		No effect
## 8	No	No	Unknown		Susceptibility
## 9	No	No	Unknown		Susceptibility
## 10	Yes	Yes	None	Constitutive	overcompensation
## 11	No	No	Unknown		No effect
## 12	No	Yes	None		No effect
## 13	Yes	No	Unknown		No effect
## 14	Yes	No	Unknown		No effect
## 15	Yes	No	Unknown		No effect
## 16	Yes	Yes	None		No effect
## 17	Yes	Yes	None	Constitutive	overcompensation
## 18	Yes	No	Neg		Overcompensation
## 19	Yes	No	Neg		Compensation
## 20	Yes	No	Neg		Compensation
## 21	Yes	No	Neg		Overcompensation
## 22	No	Yes	None	Constitutive	susceptibility
## 23	No	No	Unknown		Uncategorized tolerance
## 24	No	Yes	None		No effect
## 25	Yes	Yes	Neg	Constitutive	susceptibility
## 26	Yes	Yes	Neg		No effect
## 27	Yes	Yes	Neg		No effect
## 29	No	No	Unknown		No effect
## 30	No	No	Unknown		Uncategorized tolerance
## 31	No	No	None		No effect
## 32	Yes	Yes	None		No effect
## 33	Yes	Yes	None		No effect
## 34	Yes	Yes	Neg		No effect
## 35	Yes	Yes	Neg		No effect
## 36	Yes	Yes	Neg		No effect
## 37	Yes	Yes	Neg		No effect
## 38	No	Yes	None		No effect
## 39	No	No	Pos		Overcompensation
## 40	No	No	None		Susceptibility
## 41	No	No	Neg		Partial compensation
## 42	No	Yes	None		No effect
## 43	No	Yes	None		No effect
## 44	No	Yes	Neg		No effect
## 45	No	Yes	Neg		No effect
## 46	No	Yes	None		No effect

## 47	No	Yes	None	No effect
## 48	No	Yes	None	No effect
## 49	No	No	Unknown	Uncategorized tolerance
## 50	Yes	Yes	Neg	No effect
## 51	Yes	Yes	Neg	No effect
## 52	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect
## 53	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect
## 54	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect
## 55	Yes	Yes	Neg	Constitutive overcompensation
## 56	Yes	Yes	Neg	Constitutive overcompensation
## 57	Yes	Yes	None	Constitutive overcompensation
## 58	Yes	Yes	None	Constitutive overcompensation
## 59	Yes	Yes	Neg	No effect
## 60	No	Yes	Neg	Constitutive susceptibility
## 61	Yes	Yes	Neg	Induced compensation
## 62	No	Yes	None	Constitutive overcompensation
## 63	No	No	Unknown	Uncategorized tolerance
## 64	No	No	Unknown	No effect
## 65	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect
## 66	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect
## 67	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect
## 68	Yes	No	Unknown	Uncategorized tolerance
## 69	Yes	No	Unknown	Susceptibility
## 70	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect
## 71	Yes	Yes	None	Constitutive overcompensation
## 72	Yes	Yes	None	No effect
## 73	Yes	Yes	None	No effect
## 74	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect
## 75	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect
## 76	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect
## 77	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect
## 78	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect
## 79	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect
## 80	No	Yes	None	No effect
## 81	No	Yes	Neg	No effect
## 82	No	Yes	None	Constitutive overcompensation
## 83	No	Yes	Pos	Constitutive overcompensation
## 84	No	Yes	Neg	Induced partial compensation
## 85	No	Yes	None	Constitutive overcompensation
## 86	No	Yes	None	No effect
## 87	No	No	Unknown	No effect
## 88	No	Yes	Neg	Constitutive overcompensation
## 89	No	Yes	Neg	Constitutive compensation
## 90	No	No	Unknown	No effect
## 91	No	Yes	Pos	No effect
## 92	No	Yes	None	No effect
## 93	No	Yes	Neg	No effect
## 94	No	Yes	Neg	Induced compensation
## 95	Yes	Yes	Neg	Constitutive overcompensation
## 96	No	Yes	None	No effect
## 97	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect
## 98	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect
## 100	No	Yes	None	No effect
## 101	No	Yes	None	Constitutive overcompensation

## 102	Yes	No	Neg	Compensation	
## 103	Yes	No	Neg	Partial compensation	
## 104	Yes	Yes	None	Constitutive overcompensation	
## 105	Yes	Yes	None	Constitutive overcompensation	
## 106	Yes	Yes	None	No effect	
## 107	No	No	None	No effect	
## 108	No	No	None	No effect	
## 109	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect	
## 110	Yes	No	Unknown	No effect	
## 111	Yes	Yes	Neg	No effect	
## 112	Yes	Yes	Neg	No effect	
## 113	Yes	Yes	Neg	No effect	
##	InFit	UniformHerbivory	InFeGu	RoShHe	PlFuGu
## 1	Positive	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 2	No effect	Yes	Chewing	Whole plant	Cultivated
## 3	No effect	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 4	No effect	No	Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 5	Positive	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 6	No effect	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 7	No effect	Yes	Chewing	Root	Cultivated
## 8	Negative	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 9	Positive	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 10	Unknown	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 11	No effect	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 12	No effect	Yes	Piercing-sucking	Shoot	Cultivated
## 13	Unknown	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 14	Unknown	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 15	Unknown	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 16	No effect	Yes	Chewing	Root	Cultivated
## 17	No effect	Yes	Chewing	Root	Cultivated
## 18	Negative	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 19	Negative	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 20	Negative	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 21	Negative	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 22	No effect	No	Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 23	No effect	Yes	Chewing	Root	Uncultivated
## 24	No effect	Yes	Piercing-sucking	Shoot	Cultivated
## 25	Positive	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 26	No effect	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 27	No effect	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 29	Positive	No	Mixed community	Whole plant	Cultivated
## 30	No effect	No	Mixed community	Whole plant	Cultivated
## 31	Negative	No	Mixed community	Whole plant	Cultivated
## 32	No effect	No	Galling	Shoot	Cultivated
## 33	No effect	No	Galling	Shoot	Cultivated
## 34	No effect	No	Galling	Shoot	Cultivated
## 35	No effect	No	Galling	Shoot	Cultivated
## 36	No effect	No	Galling	Shoot	Cultivated
## 37	No effect	No	Galling	Shoot	Cultivated
## 38	Unknown	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 39	Mixed	No	Mixed community	Whole plant	Cultivated
## 40	Mixed	No	Mixed community	Whole plant	Cultivated
## 41	Negative	No	Mixed community	Whole plant	Cultivated
## 42	Unknown	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated

## 43	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 44	No effect	No		Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 45	Positive	No	Mixed community	Whole plant		Cultivated
## 46	Positive	No	Mixed community	Whole plant		Cultivated
## 47	Positive	No	Mixed community	Whole plant		Cultivated
## 48	No effect	No	Mixed community	Whole plant		Cultivated
## 49	No effect	Yes		Chewing	Root	Uncultivated
## 50	Positive	Yes		Chewing	Root	Uncultivated
## 51	Positive	Yes		Chewing	Root	Uncultivated
## 52	No effect	Yes	Piercing-sucking		Shoot	Cultivated
## 53	No effect	Yes	Piercing-sucking		Shoot	Cultivated
## 54	Negative	Yes	Piercing-sucking		Shoot	Cultivated
## 55	Mixed	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 56	Mixed	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 57	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 58	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 59	Positive	Yes		Chewing	Root	Uncultivated
## 60	Negative	No	Mixed community	Whole plant		Uncultivated
## 61	No effect	Yes		Chewing	Root	Cultivated
## 62	No effect	No		Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 63	No effect	No	Mixed community	Whole plant		Cultivated
## 64	No effect	No	Mixed community	Whole plant		Cultivated
## 65	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 66	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 67	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 68	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 69	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 70	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 71	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 72	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 73	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 74	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 75	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 76	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 77	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 78	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 79	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 80	Negative	No	Mixed community	Whole plant		Uncultivated
## 81	No effect	No		Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 82	Positive	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 83	Unknown	Yes	Piercing-sucking		Shoot	Cultivated
## 84	No effect	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 85	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 86	No effect	Yes	Piercing-sucking		Shoot	Cultivated
## 87	Positive	No	Mixed community	Whole plant		Cultivated
## 88	Negative	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 89	No effect	Yes		Chewing	Root	Cultivated
## 90	Negative	No	Mixed community	Whole plant		Cultivated
## 91	Negative	Yes		Chewing	Root	Cultivated
## 92	Unknown	Yes		Chewing	Root	Cultivated
## 93	No effect	No		Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 94	Positive	Yes	Piercing-sucking		Shoot	Cultivated
## 95	Positive	Yes		Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 96	No effect	No		Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated

## 97	No effect	No	Mixed community	Whole plant	Cultivated
## 98	No effect	No	Mixed community	Whole plant	Cultivated
## 100	No effect	Yes	Piercing-sucking	Shoot	Cultivated
## 101	No effect	No	Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 102	Negative	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 103	Negative	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 104	Unknown	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 105	Unknown	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 106	Unknown	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Cultivated
## 107	Negative	Yes	Chewing	Root	Uncultivated
## 108	Negative	Yes	Chewing	Root	Uncultivated
## 109	No effect	No	Mixed community	Whole plant	Cultivated
## 110	Positive	No	Mixed community	Whole plant	Cultivated
## 111	No effect	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 112	No effect	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
## 113	No effect	Yes	Chewing	Shoot	Uncultivated
##	MiSource		MiFuGu	CoCoSppRichness	CoCoSimple
## 1	Commercial		AMF	4	Small consortia
## 2	Academic stock		Other PGPF	Max	Complex
## 3	Academic stock		Other PGPF	Max	Complex
## 4	Field isolate		AMF	Max	Complex
## 5	Commercial		AMF	4	Small consortia
## 6	Commercial		AMF	4	Small consortia
## 7	Field isolate		AMF	1	Single
## 8	Commercial		AMF	4	Small consortia
## 9	Commercial		AMF	4	Small consortia
## 10	Academic stock		AMF	1	Single
## 11	Commercial		AMF	4	Small consortia
## 12	Unknown		AMF	Unknown	Unknown
## 13	Academic stock		PGPB	1	Single
## 14	Academic stock		Mixed	Max	Complex
## 15	Academic stock		Mixed	Max	Complex
## 16	Commercial	Endophytic entomopathogen		1	Single
## 17	Mixed		Mixed	2	Small consortia
## 18	Academic stock	Endophytic entomopathogen		Max	Complex
## 19	Academic stock	Endophytic entomopathogen		Max	Complex
## 20	Academic stock		Mixed	Max	Complex
## 21	Academic stock		Mixed	Max	Complex
## 22	Field isolate		AMF	Max	Complex
## 23	Commercial		PGPB	Max	Complex
## 24	Unknown		AMF	Unknown	Unknown
## 25	Field isolate		Unknown	Max	Complex
## 26	Field isolate		Unknown	Max	Complex
## 27	Field isolate		Unknown	Max	Complex
## 29	Commercial		AMF	Max	Complex
## 30	Commercial		AMF	Max	Complex
## 31	Commercial		AMF	Max	Complex
## 32	Commercial		N-fixing	1	Single
## 33	Commercial		Mixed	2	Small consortia
## 34	Commercial		AMF	1	Single
## 35	Commercial		N-fixing	1	Single
## 36	Commercial		Mixed	2	Small consortia
## 37	Commercial		AMF	1	Single
## 38	Commercial		AMF	1	Single

## 39	Commercial	AMF	Max	Complex
## 40	Commercial	AMF	Max	Complex
## 41	Commercial	AMF	Max	Complex
## 42	Commercial	AMF	1	Single
## 43	Commercial	AMF	1	Single
## 44	Field isolate	AMF	Max	Complex
## 45	Commercial	AMF	Max	Complex
## 46	Commercial	AMF	Max	Complex
## 47	Commercial	AMF	Max	Complex
## 48	Commercial	AMF	Max	Complex
## 49	Commercial	PGPB	Max	Complex
## 50	Unknown	Mixed	3	Small consortia
## 51	Unknown	Mixed	4	Small consortia
## 52	Commercial	N-fixing	1	Single
## 53	Commercial	N-fixing	2	Small consortia
## 54	Commercial	Mixed	2	Small consortia
## 55	Lab stock	AMF	1	Single
## 56	Lab stock	Mixed	2	Small consortia
## 57	Academic stock	AMF	1	Single
## 58	Academic stock	AMF	3	Small consortia
## 59	Unknown	Mixed	3	Small consortia
## 60	Field isolate	Mixed	Max	Complex
## 61	Academic stock	Other PGPF	Max	Complex
## 62	Field isolate	AMF	Max	Complex
## 63	Commercial	AMF	Max	Complex
## 64	Commercial	AMF	Max	Complex
## 65	Academic stock	PGPB	1	Single
## 66	Academic stock	Mixed	Max	Complex
## 67	Academic stock	Mixed	Max	Complex
## 68	Academic stock	PGPB	1	Single
## 69	Academic stock	Mixed	Max	Complex
## 70	Academic stock	Mixed	Max	Complex
## 71	Unknown	AMF	1	Single
## 72	Unknown	AMF	1	Single
## 73	Unknown	AMF	1	Single
## 74	Academic stock	PGPB	1	Single
## 75	Academic stock	Mixed	Max	Complex
## 76	Academic stock	Mixed	Max	Complex
## 77	Academic stock	PGPB	1	Single
## 78	Academic stock	Mixed	Max	Complex
## 79	Academic stock	Mixed	Max	Complex
## 80	Field isolate	Mixed	Max	Complex
## 81	Field isolate	AMF	Max	Complex
## 82	Commercial	AMF	1	Single
## 83	Academic stock	AMF	1	Single
## 84	Unknown	PGPB	1	Single
## 85	Academic stock	AMF	2	Small consortia
## 86	Field isolate	AMF	Max	Complex
## 87	Commercial	Other PGPF	Max	Complex
## 88	Unknown	Other PGPF	Unknown	Unknown
## 89	Unknown	Other PGPF	1	Single
## 90	Commercial	Other PGPF	Max	Complex
## 91	Commercial	AMF	4	Small consortia
## 92	Field isolate	Other PGPF	1	Single

## 93	Field isolate		AMF	Max	Complex
## 94	Commercial		AMF	1	Single
## 95	Lab stock		N-fixing	1	Single
## 96	Field isolate		AMF	Max	Complex
## 97	Commercial		Mixed	Max	Complex
## 98	Commercial		Mixed	Max	Complex
## 100	Unknown		AMF	Unknown	Unknown
## 101	Field isolate		AMF	Max	Complex
## 102	Academic stock		Other PGPF	Max	Complex
## 103	Academic stock		Other PGPF	Max	Complex
## 104	Unknown		AMF	1	Single
## 105	Unknown		AMF	1	Single
## 106	Unknown		AMF	1	Single
## 107	Commercial		PGPB	Max	Complex
## 108	Commercial		PGPB	Max	Complex
## 109	Commercial		Mixed	Max	Complex
## 110	Commercial		Mixed	Max	Complex
## 111	Field isolate		Unknown	Max	Complex
## 112	Field isolate		Unknown	Max	Complex
## 113	Field isolate		Unknown	Max	Complex
##	BaFu	RegrowthPeriod	RegrowthPeriodDuration_inDays		Environ
## 1	Fungi	Yes	40		Greenhouse
## 2	Fungi	No	0		Greenhouse
## 3	Fungi	No	0		Greenhouse
## 4	Fungi	Yes	28		Greenhouse
## 5	Fungi	Yes	40		Greenhouse
## 6	Fungi	Yes	40		Greenhouse
## 7	Fungi	No	0		Greenhouse
## 8	Fungi	Yes	40		Greenhouse
## 9	Fungi	Yes	40		Greenhouse
## 10	Fungi	Yes	91		Greenhouse
## 11	Fungi	Yes	40		Greenhouse
## 12	Fungi	No	0		Greenhouse
## 13	Bacteria	No	0		Greenhouse
## 14	Bacteria	No	0		Greenhouse
## 15	Bacteria	No	0		Greenhouse
## 16	Fungi	No	0		Greenhouse
## 17	Fungi	No	0		Greenhouse
## 18	Fungi	No	0		Experimental station
## 19	Fungi	No	0		Experimental station
## 20	Fungi	No	0		Experimental station
## 21	Fungi	No	0		Experimental station
## 22	Fungi	Yes	28		Greenhouse
## 23	Bacteria	No	0		Greenhouse
## 24	Fungi	No	0		Greenhouse
## 25	Mixed	Yes	60		Greenhouse
## 26	Mixed	Yes	60		Greenhouse
## 27	Bacteria	Yes	60		Greenhouse
## 29	Fungi	No	0		Experimental station
## 30	Fungi	No	0		Experimental station
## 31	Fungi	No	0		Field
## 32	Bacteria	No	0		Greenhouse
## 33	Mixed	No	0		Greenhouse
## 34	Fungi	No	0		Greenhouse

## 35	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 36	Mixed	No	0	Greenhouse
## 37	Fungi	No	0	Greenhouse
## 38	Fungi	Yes	35	Experimental station
## 39	Fungi	No	0	Field
## 40	Fungi	No	0	Field
## 41	Fungi	No	0	Field
## 42	Fungi	Yes	35	Experimental station
## 43	Fungi	Yes	35	Experimental station
## 44	Fungi	Yes	28	Greenhouse
## 45	Fungi	No	0	Experimental station
## 46	Fungi	No	0	Experimental station
## 47	Fungi	No	0	Experimental station
## 48	Fungi	No	0	Experimental station
## 49	Bacteria	No	0	Growth chamber
## 50	Mixed	No	0	Growth chamber
## 51	Mixed	No	0	Growth chamber
## 52	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 53	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 54	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 55	Fungi	No	0	Greenhouse
## 56	Mixed	No	0	Greenhouse
## 57	Fungi	Yes	91	Greenhouse
## 58	Fungi	Yes	91	Greenhouse
## 59	Mixed	No	0	Growth chamber
## 60	Fungi	No	0	Other field
## 61	Fungi	No	0	Greenhouse
## 62	Fungi	Yes	28	Greenhouse
## 63	Fungi	No	0	Agricultural field
## 64	Fungi	No	0	Agricultural field
## 65	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 66	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 67	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 68	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 69	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 70	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 71	Fungi	No	0	Greenhouse
## 72	Fungi	No	0	Greenhouse
## 73	Fungi	No	0	Greenhouse
## 74	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 75	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 76	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 77	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 78	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 79	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 80	Fungi	No	0	Other field
## 81	Fungi	Yes	28	Greenhouse
## 82	Fungi	No	0	Greenhouse
## 83	Fungi	No	0	Growth chamber
## 84	Bacteria	No	0	Growth chamber
## 85	Fungi	No	0	Greenhouse
## 86	Fungi	No	0	Greenhouse
## 87	Fungi	No	0	Experimental station
## 88	Fungi	No	0	Greenhouse

## 89	Fungi	No	0	Greenhouse
## 90	Fungi	No	0	Experimental station
## 91	Fungi	No	0	Other field
## 92	Fungi	No	0	Growth chamber
## 93	Fungi	Yes	28	Greenhouse
## 94	Fungi	No	0	Greenhouse
## 95	Bacteria	No	0	Greenhouse
## 96	Fungi	Yes	28	Greenhouse
## 97	Mixed	No	0	Agricultural field
## 98	Mixed	No	0	Agricultural field
## 100	Fungi	No	0	Greenhouse
## 101	Fungi	Yes	28	Greenhouse
## 102	Fungi	No	0	Experimental station
## 103	Fungi	No	0	Experimental station
## 104	Fungi	No	0	Greenhouse
## 105	Fungi	No	0	Greenhouse
## 106	Fungi	No	0	Greenhouse
## 107	Bacteria	No	0	Other field
## 108	Bacteria	No	0	Other field
## 109	Mixed	No	0	Agricultural field
## 110	Mixed	No	0	Agricultural field
## 111	Mixed	Yes	60	Greenhouse
## 112	Mixed	Yes	60	Greenhouse
## 113	Bacteria	Yes	60	Greenhouse
##				Insect.experimental.treatment
## 1				1. D. perplexus
## 2				1. Uninfested controls\n2. Adult and larval L. oryzoophilus
## 3				1. Uninfested controls\n2. Adult L. oryzoophilus
## 4				1. Uninfested control\n2. M. bivittatus
## 5				1. D. perplexus
## 6				1. D. perplexus
## 7				1. Uninfested control\n2. P. vetula
## 8				1. D. perplexus
## 9				1. D. perplexus
## 10				1. Uninfested control\n2. J. coenia
## 11				1. D. perplexus
## 12				1. Uninfested control\n2. R. padi
## 13				1. H. zea
## 14				1. H. zea
## 15				1. H. zea
## 16				1. Uninfested control\n2. P. vetula
## 17				1. Uninfested control\n2. P. vetula
## 18				1. Uninfested control\n2. O. furnacalis
## 19				1. Uninfested control\n2. O. furnacalis
## 20				1. Uninfested control\n2. O. furnacalis
## 21				1. Uninfested control\n2. O. furnacalis
## 22				1. Uninfested control\n2. M. bivittatus
## 23				1. Popillia japonica
## 24				1. Uninfested control\n2. R. padi
## 25				1. Uninfested control\n2. G. inexacta
## 26				1. Uninfested control\n2. G. inexacta
## 27				1. Uninfested control\n2. G. inexacta
## 29				1. Insects-present
## 30				1. Insects-present

31 1. Control\n2. Insecticide and fungicide
 ## 32 1. Uninfested control\n2. M. destructor
 ## 33 1. Uninfested control\n2. M. destructor
 ## 34 1. Uninfested control\n2. M. destructor
 ## 35 1. Uninfested control\n2. M. destructor
 ## 36 1. Uninfested control\n2. M. destructor
 ## 37 1. Uninfested control\n2. M. destructor
 ## 38 1. Uninfested control\n2. V. cardui
 ## 39 1. Control\n2. Insecticide and fungicide
 ## 40 1. Control\n2. Insecticide and fungicide
 ## 41 1. Control\n2. Insecticide and fungicide
 ## 42 1. Uninfested control\n2. V. cardui
 ## 43 1. Uninfested control\n2. V. cardui
 ## 44 1. Uninfested control\n2. M. bivittatus
 ## 45 1. No-insecticide control\n2. Insecticide
 ## 46 1. No-insecticide control\n2. Insecticide
 ## 47 1. No-insecticide control\n2. Insecticide
 ## 48 1. No-insecticide control\n2. Insecticide
 ## 49 1. Popillia japonica
 ## 50 1. Uninfested control\n2. S. lepidus
 ## 51 1. Uninfested control\n2. S. lepidus
 ## 52 1. A. glycines
 ## 53 1. A. glycines
 ## 54 1. A. glycines
 ## 55 1. Uninfested control\n2. S. litura
 ## 56 1. Uninfested control\n2. S. litura
 ## 57 1. Uninfested control\n2. J. coenia
 ## 58 1. Uninfested control\n2. J. coenia
 ## 59 1. Uninfested control\n2. S. lepidus
 ## 60 1. Untreated control\n2. Insecticide-treated
 ## 61 1. Uninfested controls\n2. Larval L. oryzophilus
 ## 62 1. Uninfested control\n2. M. bivittatus
 ## 63 1. Insects-present
 ## 64 1. Insects-present
 ## 65 1. H. zea
 ## 66 1. H. zea
 ## 67 1. H. zea
 ## 68 1. H. zea
 ## 69 1. H. zea
 ## 70 1. H. zea
 ## 71 1. Uninfested control\n2. S. exigua
 ## 72 1. Uninfested control\n2. S. exigua
 ## 73 1. Uninfested control\n2. S. exigua
 ## 74 1. H. zea
 ## 75 1. H. zea
 ## 76 1. H. zea
 ## 77 1. H. zea
 ## 78 1. H. zea
 ## 79 1. H. zea
 ## 80 1. Untreated control\n2. Insecticide-treated
 ## 81 1. Uninfested control\n2. M. bivittatus
 ## 82 1. Uninfested control\n2. S. exigua
 ## 83 1. Uninfested control\n2. A. pisum
 ## 84 1. Uninfested control\n2. M. brassicae

85 1. No-damage control\n2. Mechanical damage\n3. Mechanical damage with *M. sexta* regurgitant
86 1. Uninfested control\n2. *P. spumarius*
87 1. Insects-present
88 1. Uninfested control\n2. *C. medinalis*
89 1. Uninfested control\n2. *P. vetula*
90 1. Insects-present
91 1. Uninfested control\n2. *D. albohirum*
92 1. Uninfested control\n2. *A. vitattum*
93 1. Uninfested control\n2. *M. bivittatus*
94 1. Uninfested control\n2. *B. tabaci*
95 1. Uninfested control\n2. *S. litura*
96 1. Uninfested control\n2. *M. bivittatus*
97 1. Natural infestation
98 1. Natural infestation
100 1. Uninfested control\n2. *R. padi*
101 1. Uninfested control\n2. *M. bivittatus*
102 1. Uninfested control\n2. *O. furnacalis*
103 1. Uninfested control\n2. *O. furnacalis*
104 1. Uninfested control\n2. *S. exigua*
105 1. Uninfested control\n2. *S. exigua*
106 1. Uninfested control\n2. *S. exigua*
107 1. Uninfested control\n2. *N. vicinus*
108 1. Uninfested control\n2. *N. vicinus*
109 1. Natural infestation
110 1. Natural infestation
111 1. Uninfested control\n2. *H. bicallosicollis*
112 1. Uninfested control\n2. *H. bicallosicollis*
113 1. Uninfested control\n2. *H. bicallosicollis*
Plant..Family.
1 *Asclepias curassavica*\nTropical milkweed\n(Apocynaceae)
2 *Oryza sativa*\nRice\n(Poaceae)
3 *Oryza sativa*\nRice\n(Poaceae)
4 *Andropogon gerardii* \nBig bluestem\n(Poaceae)
5 *Asclepias incarnata*\nSwamp milkweed\n(Apocynaceae)
6 *Asclepias latifolia*\nBroadleaf milkweed\n(Apocynaceae)
7 *Zea mays*\nHybrid corn\n(Poaceae)
8 *Asclepias purpurascens*\nPurple milkweed\n(Apocynaceae)
9 *Asclepias syriaca*\nCommon milkweed\n(Apocynaceae)
10 *Plantago lanceolata*\nNarrowleaf plantain\n(Plantaginaceae)
11 *Asclepias verticillata*\nWhorled milkweed\n(Apocynaceae)
12 *Triticum aestivum* cv. Avalon\nWheat\n(Poaceae)
13 *Zea mays*\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
14 *Zea mays*\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
15 *Zea mays*\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
16 *Zea mays*\nHybrid corn\n(Poaceae)
17 *Zea mays*\nHybrid corn\n(Poaceae)
18 *Zea mays*\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
19 *Zea mays*\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
20 *Zea mays*\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
21 *Zea mays*\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
22 *Brickellia eupatorioides* \nFalse boneset\n(Asteraceae)
23 *Cynodon dactylon* × *Cynodon transvaalensis*\nHybrid bermudagrass\n(Poaceae)
24 *Triticum aestivum* cv. Cadenza\nWheat\n(Poaceae)
25 *Triadica sebifera*\nChinese tallow\n(Euphorbiaceae)

26 Triadica sebifera\nChinese tallow\n(Euphorbiaceae)
 ## 27 Triadica sebifera\nChinese tallow\n(Euphorbiaceae)
 ## 29 Oryza sativa\nRice\n(Poaceae)
 ## 30 Oryza sativa\nRice\n(Poaceae)
 ## 31 Capsicum annuum \nSweet pepper\n(Solanaceae)
 ## 32 Triticum aestivum subsp. aestivum cv. Molly\nHard red winter wheat\n(Poaceae)
 ## 33 Triticum aestivum subsp. aestivum cv. Molly\nHard red winter wheat\n(Poaceae)
 ## 34 Triticum aestivum subsp. aestivum cv. Molly\nHard red winter wheat\n(Poaceae)
 ## 35 Triticum aestivum subsp. aestivum cv. Newton\nHard red winter wheat\n(Poaceae)
 ## 36 Triticum aestivum subsp. aestivum cv. Newton\nHard red winter wheat\n(Poaceae)
 ## 37 Triticum aestivum subsp. aestivum cv. Newton\nHard red winter wheat\n(Poaceae)
 ## 38 Fragaria × ananassa\nStrawberry\n(Rosaceae)
 ## 39 Capsicum annuum \nSweet pepper\n(Solanaceae)
 ## 40 Capsicum annuum \nSweet pepper\n(Solanaceae)
 ## 41 Capsicum annuum \nSweet pepper\n(Solanaceae)
 ## 42 Fragaria × ananassa\nStrawberry\n(Rosaceae)
 ## 43 Fragaria × ananassa\nStrawberry\n(Rosaceae)
 ## 44 Elymus canadensis \nCanada wild-rye\n(Poaceae)
 ## 45 Oryza sativa\nRice\n(Poaceae)
 ## 46 Oryza sativa\nRice\n(Poaceae)
 ## 47 Oryza sativa\nRice\n(Poaceae)
 ## 48 Oryza sativa\nRice\n(Poaceae)
 ## 49 Festuca arundinacea\nTall fescue\n(Poaceae)
 ## 50 Trifolium repens\nWhite clover\n(Fabaceae)
 ## 51 Trifolium repens\nWhite clover\n(Fabaceae)
 ## 52 Glycine max\nSoybean\n(Fabaceae)
 ## 53 Glycine max\nSoybean\n(Fabaceae)
 ## 54 Glycine max\nSoybean\n(Fabaceae)
 ## 55 Vigna mungo\nBlackgram\n(Fabaceae)
 ## 56 Vigna mungo\nBlackgram\n(Fabaceae)
 ## 57 Plantago lanceolata\nNarrowleaf plantain\n(Plantaginaceae)
 ## 58 Plantago lanceolata\nNarrowleaf plantain\n(Plantaginaceae)
 ## 59 Trifolium repens\nWhite clover\n(Fabaceae)
 ## 60 Jacobaea vulgaris\nRagwort\n(Asteraceae)
 ## 61 Oryza sativa\nRice\n(Poaceae)
 ## 62 Lespedeza capitata\nRound-headed bush clover\n(Fabaceae)
 ## 63 Oryza sativa\nRice\n(Poaceae)
 ## 64 Oryza sativa\nRice\n(Poaceae)
 ## 65 Zea mays\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
 ## 66 Zea mays\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
 ## 67 Zea mays\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
 ## 68 Zea mays\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
 ## 69 Zea mays\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
 ## 70 Zea mays\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
 ## 71 Arachis hypogaea\nPeanut\n(Fabaceae)\n
 ## 72 Arachis hypogaea\nPeanut\n(Fabaceae)\n
 ## 73 Arachis hypogaea\nPeanut\n(Fabaceae)\n
 ## 74 Zea mays\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
 ## 75 Zea mays\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
 ## 76 Zea mays\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
 ## 77 Zea mays\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
 ## 78 Zea mays\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
 ## 79 Zea mays\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
 ## 80 Plantago lanceolata\nNarrowleaf plantain\n(Plantaginaceae)

81 Pascopyrum smithii \nWestern wheatgrass\n(Poaceae)
 ## 82 Medicago truncatula\nBarrel medic\n(Fabaceae)
 ## 83 Medicago sativa\nAlfalfa\n(Fabaceae)
 ## 84 Arabidopsis thaliana Col-0\nArabidopsis\n(Brassicaceae)
 ## 85 Solanum lycopersicum\nTomato\n(Solanaceae)
 ## 86 Fragaria × ananassa\nStrawberry\n(Rosaceae)
 ## 87 Solanum lycopersicum\nTomato\n(Solanaceae)
 ## 88 Oryza sativa\nRice\n(Poaceae)
 ## 89 Zea mays\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
 ## 90 Cucurbita pepo\nZucchini\n(Cucurbitaceae)
 ## 91 Saccharum spp. hybrid\nSugarcane\n(Poaceae)
 ## 92 Cucumis sativus\nCucumber \n(Cucurbitaceae)
 ## 93 Rudbeckia hirta\nBlack-eyed Susan\n(Asteraceae)
 ## 94 Capsicum chinense\nHabanero pepper\n(Solanaceae)
 ## 95 Vigna mungo\nBlackgram\n(Fabaceae)
 ## 96 Salvia azurea\nBlue sage\n(Lamiaceae)
 ## 97 Glycine max\nSoybean\n(Fabaceae)
 ## 98 Glycine max\nSoybean\n(Fabaceae)
 ## 100 Triticum aestivum cv. Skyfall\nWheat\n(Poaceae)
 ## 101 Sorghastrum nutans\nIndiangrass\n(Poaceae)
 ## 102 Zea mays\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
 ## 103 Zea mays\nCorn\n(Poaceae)
 ## 104 Solanum lycopersicum\nTomato\n(Solanaceae)
 ## 105 Solanum lycopersicum\nTomato\n(Solanaceae)
 ## 106 Solanum lycopersicum\nTomato\n(Solanaceae)
 ## 107 Cynodon dactylon × Cynodon transvaalensis\nTifway hybrid bermudagrass\n(Poaceae)
 ## 108 Cynodon dactylon × Cynodon transvaalensis\nTifway hybrid bermudagrass\n(Poaceae)
 ## 109 Glycine max\nSoybean\n(Fabaceae)
 ## 110 Glycine max\nSoybean\n(Fabaceae)
 ## 111 Triadica sebifera\nChinese tallow\n(Euphorbiaceae)
 ## 112 Triadica sebifera\nChinese tallow\n(Euphorbiaceae)
 ## 113 Triadica sebifera\nChinese tallow\n(Euphorbiaceae)

 ## 1
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Microbia
 1. Sterilized-inocul
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 1. No-inoculant c
 1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitud
 1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitud
 1. No-inoculant control with sterilized s
 1. No-inoculant contr
 1. No-inoculant control\n2. Beauveria
 1. No-inoculant control\n2
 1. No-inoculant control\n2
 1. No-inoculant control\n2. B. bassiana and
 1. No-inoculant control\n2. B. bassiana and


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## 77      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 78      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 79      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 80      1. Untreated soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 81      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 82      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 83      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 84      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 85      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 86      1. Filtrate soil (AMF spores removed)\n2. Soil and root pieces
## 87      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 88      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 89      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 90      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 91      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 92      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 93      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 94      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 95      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 96      1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 97      1. Control (no inoculant)\n2. R. irregularis, B. altitudinis
## 98      1. Control (no inoculant)\n2. R. irregularis, B. altitudinis
## 100     1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 101     1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 102     1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 103     1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 104     1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 105     1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 106     1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 107     1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 108     1. No-inoculant control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 109     1. Control (no inoculant)\n2. R. irregularis, B. altitudinis
## 110     1. Control (no inoculant)\n2. R. irregularis, B. altitudinis
## 111     1. Sterilized control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 112     1. Sterilized control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis
## 113     1. Sterilized control with sterilized soil\n2. B. altitudinis

```

##	Measure	ES.Category	TC.Mean	TC.SD	TC.SE
## 1	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA
## 2	Shoot fresh weight	Shoot	10.9274471	1.72437151	0.60965739
## 3	Shoot fresh weight	Shoot	10.9274471	1.72437151	0.60965739
## 4	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	5.3404255	2.21276596	0.55319149
## 5	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA
## 6	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA
## 7	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	0.9542200	0.14614619	0.06535856
## 8	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA
## 9	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA
## 10	Total dry weight	Total	1.7463287	0.74546287	0.28175848
## 11	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA
## 12	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	2.8447196	0.24556202	NA
## 13	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA
## 14	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA
## 15	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA
## 16	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	0.9542200	0.14614619	0.06535856
## 17	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	0.9542200	0.14614619	0.06535856

## 18	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	20.5600000	0.50000000	NA
## 19	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	21.2700000	0.80000000	NA
## 20	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	20.5600000	0.50000000	NA
## 21	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	21.2700000	0.80000000	NA
## 22	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	9.6462094	3.72563177	0.93140794
## 23	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	NA	NA	NA
## 24	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	2.2811415	0.20696195	NA
## 25	Total dry weight	Total	4.1974468	1.26742236	0.18893617
## 26	Total dry weight	Total	4.1974468	1.26742236	0.18893617
## 27	Total dry weight	Total	4.1974468	1.26742236	0.18893617
## 29	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	NA	NA	NA
## 30	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	NA	NA	NA
## 31	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	179.4000000	34.78505426	11.00000000
## 32	Total dry weight	Total	1.0549383	0.10352167	0.04629630
## 33	Total dry weight	Total	1.0549383	0.10352167	0.04629630
## 34	Total dry weight	Total	1.0549383	0.10352167	0.04629630
## 35	Total dry weight	Total	0.9647564	0.12109365	0.05415473
## 36	Total dry weight	Total	0.9647564	0.12109365	0.05415473
## 37	Total dry weight	Total	0.9647564	0.12109365	0.05415473
## 38	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	84.6385542	45.90978044	13.25301205
## 39	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	277.9000000	35.10128203	11.10000000
## 40	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	373.7000000	55.97231458	17.70000000
## 41	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	970.8000000	92.33850768	29.20000000
## 42	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	99.3975904	54.25701325	15.66265060
## 43	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	75.6024096	41.73616404	12.04819277
## 44	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	4.1167048	1.12585812	0.28146453
## 45	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	2645.4024288	221.39188249	70.01026042
## 46	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	1248.5158262	285.77317872	90.36941389
## 47	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	2956.8094835	96.53239633	30.52622404
## 48	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	2140.7406378	353.86573484	111.90217077
## 49	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	NA	NA	NA
## 50	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	0.9503577	0.11992479	0.03792355
## 51	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	0.9503577	0.11992479	0.03792355
## 52	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	NA	NA	NA
## 53	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	NA	NA	NA
## 54	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	NA	NA	NA
## 55	Total fresh weight	Total	2.8369748	0.03493212	0.02016807
## 56	Total fresh weight	Total	2.8369748	0.03493212	0.02016807
## 57	Total dry weight	Total	1.7463287	0.74546287	0.28175848
## 58	Total dry weight	Total	1.7463287	0.74546287	0.28175848
## 59	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	0.9503577	0.11992479	0.03792355
## 60	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	166.0092807	99.07109372	25.58004640
## 61	Shoot fresh weight	Shoot	10.9274471	1.72437151	0.60965739
## 62	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	2.1185861	1.91562144	0.47890536
## 63	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	NA	NA	NA
## 64	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	NA	NA	NA
## 65	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA
## 66	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA
## 67	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA
## 68	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA
## 69	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA
## 70	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA
## 71	Total dry weight	Total	20.2000000	2.80000000	1.40000000
## 72	Total dry weight	Total	20.2000000	2.80000000	1.40000000

## 73	Total dry weight	Total	20.2000000	2.80000000	1.40000000	
## 74	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA	
## 75	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA	
## 76	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA	
## 77	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA	
## 78	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA	
## 79	Root dry weight	Root	NA	NA	NA	
## 80	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	13.7864438	10.58687370	2.73351903	
## 81	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	4.4069401	4.20609884	1.05152471	
## 82	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	0.2510699	0.02282454	NA	
## 83	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	0.5816993	0.05751634	0.02875817	
## 84	Total fresh weight	Total	1.2613374	0.22969657	0.07263643	
## 85	Total dry weight	Total	18.8143177	1.48210291	NA	
## 86	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	0.8486383	0.39511044	0.17669876	
## 87	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	NA	NA	NA	
## 88	Shoot fresh weight	Shoot	273.2343849	59.38348168	24.24320488	
## 89	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	3.7810662	0.68417897	0.13417854	
## 90	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	NA	NA	NA	
## 91	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	17.2900000	7.83000000	NA	
## 92	Shoot fresh weight	Shoot	8.2420994	2.03125445	NA	
## 93	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	32.3563218	6.43678161	1.60919540	
## 94	Total dry weight	Total	0.5289885	0.25334754	0.04344874	
## 95	Total fresh weight	Total	2.8369748	0.03493212	0.02016807	
## 96	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	6.2911877	1.60919540	0.40229885	
## 97	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	NA	NA	NA	
## 98	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	NA	NA	NA	
## 100	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	2.1170393	0.22346301	NA	
## 101	Shoot dry weight	Shoot	5.7142857	2.68907563	0.67226891	
## 102	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	20.5600000	0.50000000	NA	
## 103	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	21.2700000	0.80000000	NA	
## 104	Total dry weight	Total	19.4000000	6.80000000	3.40000000	
## 105	Total dry weight	Total	67.5000000	6.80000000	3.40000000	
## 106	Total dry weight	Total	67.5000000	6.80000000	3.40000000	
## 107	Root dry weight	Root	5.9100000	0.44000000	0.22000000	
## 108	Root dry weight	Root	18.3400000	1.86000000	0.93000000	
## 109	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	NA	NA	NA	
## 110	Reproductive mass	Reproductive	NA	NA	NA	
## 111	Total dry weight	Total	4.1974468	1.26742236	0.18893617	
## 112	Total dry weight	Total	4.1974468	1.26742236	0.18893617	
## 113	Total dry weight	Total	4.1974468	1.26742236	0.18893617	
##	TC.SE2B	TC.N	PlusIn.Mean	PlusIn.SD	PlusIn.SE	PlusIn.SE2B
## 1	NA	NA	5.1890756	6.904066e-01	0.12605042	5.3151260
## 2	11.5371045	8.0	6.2228932	2.622430e+00	0.92716909	7.1500623
## 3	11.5371045	8.0	9.9155877	3.128994e+00	1.10626640	11.0218541
## 4	5.8936170	16.0	4.5744681	4.085106e+00	1.02127660	5.5957447
## 5	NA	NA	7.0798319	2.071220e+00	0.37815126	7.4579832
## 6	NA	NA	1.5756303	9.205421e-01	0.16806723	1.7436975
## 7	0.9925249	5.0	0.8048345	1.275742e-01	0.05705292	0.8014950
## 8	NA	NA	5.7773109	3.106830e+00	0.56722689	6.3445378
## 9	NA	NA	8.1302521	4.487643e+00	0.81932773	8.9495798
## 10	2.0280872	7.0	1.4996305	6.276394e-01	0.23722541	1.7368559
## 11	NA	NA	2.9411765	1.610949e+00	0.29411765	3.2352941
## 12	NA	5.0	2.7927600	6.033227e-01	NA	NA
## 13	NA	NA	7.5031056	2.111070e+00	0.94409938	9.3913043

## 14	NA	NA	7.5031056	2.111070e+00	0.94409938	9.3913043
## 15	NA	NA	7.5031056	2.111070e+00	0.94409938	9.3913043
## 16	0.9925249	5.0	0.8048345	1.275742e-01	0.05705292	0.8014950
## 17	0.9925249	5.0	0.8048345	1.275742e-01	0.05705292	0.8014950
## 18	NA	3.0	16.3600000	3.000000e-01	NA	NA
## 19	NA	3.0	14.4500000	5.000000e-01	NA	NA
## 20	NA	3.0	16.3600000	3.000000e-01	NA	NA
## 21	NA	3.0	14.4500000	5.000000e-01	NA	NA
## 22	10.5776173	16.0	11.2924188	3.292419e+00	0.82310469	12.1155235
## 23	NA	NA	1.0400000	3.130495e-01	0.07000000	NA
## 24	NA	5.0	2.2311708	1.095625e-01	NA	NA
## 25	4.3863830	45.0	3.3753191	1.267422e+00	0.18893617	3.5642553
## 26	4.3863830	45.0	3.3753191	1.267422e+00	0.18893617	3.5642553
## 27	4.3863830	45.0	3.3753191	1.267422e+00	0.18893617	3.5642553
## 29	NA	NA	2211.1204124	3.216861e+02	143.86240284	2354.9828154
## 30	NA	NA	2384.4888102	6.724914e+01	30.07472756	2414.5635378
## 31	NA	10.0	181.3000000	3.763110e+01	11.90000000	NA
## 32	1.1012346	5.0	1.0364198	1.725361e-01	0.07716049	1.1135802
## 33	1.1012346	5.0	1.0364198	1.725361e-01	0.07716049	1.1135802
## 34	1.1012346	5.0	1.0364198	1.725361e-01	0.07716049	1.1135802
## 35	1.0189112	5.0	0.3950287	1.197130e-01	0.05353728	0.4485660
## 36	1.0189112	5.0	0.3950287	1.197130e-01	0.05353728	0.4485660
## 37	1.0189112	5.0	0.3950287	1.197130e-01	0.05353728	0.4485660
## 38	97.8915663	12.0	75.7530120	4.121446e+01	11.89759036	87.6506024
## 39	NA	10.0	335.0000000	4.806662e+01	15.20000000	NA
## 40	NA	10.0	364.1000000	4.743416e+01	15.00000000	NA
## 41	NA	10.0	307.8000000	4.458812e+01	14.10000000	NA
## 42	115.0602410	12.0	83.4337349	4.643148e+01	13.40361446	96.8373494
## 43	87.6506024	12.0	58.7349398	3.182383e+01	9.18674699	67.9216868
## 44	4.3981693	16.0	1.0480549	1.016018e+00	0.25400458	1.3020595
## 45	2715.4126893	10.0	2627.1595751	1.664823e+02	52.64633757	2679.8059128
## 46	1338.8852401	10.0	1180.9486382	2.456313e+02	77.67543496	1258.6240733
## 47	2987.3357078	10.0	2866.4352602	1.235762e+02	39.07823725	2905.5134977
## 48	2252.6428088	10.0	1840.4466271	3.943725e+02	124.71153077	1965.1581579
## 49	NA	NA	2.0900000	1.478851e+00	0.27000000	NA
## 50	0.9882812	10.0	0.8127623	1.059230e-01	0.03349580	0.8462581
## 51	0.9882812	10.0	0.8127623	1.059230e-01	0.03349580	0.8462581
## 52	NA	NA	2.1400000	2.400000e-01	0.08000000	NA
## 53	NA	NA	2.1400000	2.400000e-01	0.08000000	NA
## 54	NA	NA	2.1400000	2.400000e-01	0.08000000	NA
## 55	2.8571429	3.0	2.6050420	5.239818e-02	0.03025210	2.6352941
## 56	2.8571429	3.0	2.6050420	5.239818e-02	0.03025210	2.6352941
## 57	2.0280872	7.0	1.4996305	6.276394e-01	0.23722541	1.7368559
## 58	2.0280872	7.0	1.4996305	6.276394e-01	0.23722541	1.7368559
## 59	0.9882812	10.0	0.8127623	1.059230e-01	0.03349580	0.8462581
## 60	191.5893271	15.0	74.4779582	5.054648e+01	13.05104408	87.5290023
## 61	11.5371045	8.0	7.8618999	3.764586e+00	1.33098200	9.1928819
## 62	2.5974914	16.0	2.1049031	1.450399e+00	0.36259977	2.4675029
## 63	NA	NA	3366.0306335	8.067746e+01	36.08005575	3402.1106899
## 64	NA	NA	2908.9591131	1.883196e+02	84.21909878	2993.1782119
## 65	NA	NA	5.4161491	2.055516e+00	0.91925466	7.2546584
## 66	NA	NA	5.4161491	2.055516e+00	0.91925466	7.2546584
## 67	NA	NA	5.4161491	2.055516e+00	0.91925466	7.2546584
## 68	NA	NA	7.4161491	2.638838e+00	1.18012422	9.7763975

## 69		NA	NA	7.4161491	2.638838e+00	1.18012422	9.7763975
## 70		NA	NA	7.4161491	2.638838e+00	1.18012422	9.7763975
## 71		NA	4.0	17.0000000	4.800000e+00	2.40000000	NA
## 72		NA	4.0	17.0000000	4.800000e+00	2.40000000	NA
## 73		NA	4.0	17.0000000	4.800000e+00	2.40000000	NA
## 74		NA	NA	3.9254658	5.555448e-01	0.24844721	4.4223602
## 75		NA	NA	3.9254658	5.555448e-01	0.24844721	4.4223602
## 76		NA	NA	3.9254658	5.555448e-01	0.24844721	4.4223602
## 77		NA	NA	3.5279503	9.860921e-01	0.44099379	4.4099379
## 78		NA	NA	3.5279503	9.860921e-01	0.44099379	4.4099379
## 79		NA	NA	3.5279503	9.860921e-01	0.44099379	4.4099379
## 80	16.5199629	15.0		10.3398329	8.400454e+00	2.16898793	12.5088208
## 81	5.4584648	16.0		1.1850683	1.480547e+00	0.37013670	1.5552050
## 82	0.2738944	4.0		0.2674750	6.419401e-03	NA	0.2738944
## 83	0.6104575	4.0		0.8209150	1.281046e-01	0.06405229	0.8849673
## 84	1.3339739	10.0		0.8186011	1.020874e-01	0.03228286	0.8508839
## 85	20.2964206	8.0		19.8489933	4.082774e+00	NA	23.9317673
## 86	1.0253371	5.0		0.6680609	3.266778e-01	0.13336567	0.8014266
## 87		NA	NA	62.8597786	6.998508e+00	4.04059041	66.9003690
## 88	297.4775897	6.0		178.3737822	5.653025e+01	23.07837811	201.4521603
## 89	3.9152447	26.0		3.0071559	6.490056e-01	0.12728046	3.1344363
## 90		NA	NA	2.7210884	2.943873e+00	0.34693878	3.0680272
## 91		NA	7.0	18.7750000	5.675000e+00	NA	NA
## 92		NA	8.5	5.6878841	2.011274e+00	NA	NA
## 93	33.9655172	16.0		18.1609195	4.597701e+00	1.14942529	19.3103448
## 94	0.5724372	34.0		0.3421589	2.406802e-01	0.04127631	0.3834352
## 95	2.8571429	3.0		2.6050420	5.239818e-02	0.03025210	2.6352941
## 96	6.6934866	16.0		4.6245211	2.298851e+00	0.57471264	5.1992337
## 97		NA	NA	3075.0000000	2.378142e+02	84.08000000	NA
## 98		NA	NA	3075.0000000	2.378142e+02	84.08000000	NA
## 100		NA	5.0	2.2699023	4.180574e-01	NA	NA
## 101	6.3865546	16.0		3.9495798	1.512605e+00	0.37815126	4.3277311
## 102		NA	3.0	16.3600000	3.000000e-01	NA	NA
## 103		NA	3.0	14.4500000	5.000000e-01	NA	NA
## 104		NA	4.0	17.5000000	1.000000e+00	0.50000000	NA
## 105		NA	4.0	17.5000000	1.000000e+00	0.50000000	NA
## 106		NA	4.0	17.5000000	1.000000e+00	0.50000000	NA
## 107		NA	4.0	5.7600000	2.540000e+00	1.27000000	NA
## 108		NA	4.0	12.2400000	1.480000e+00	0.74000000	NA
## 109		NA	NA	3060.0000000	1.014274e+02	35.86000000	NA
## 110		NA	NA	3060.0000000	1.014274e+02	35.86000000	NA
## 111	4.3863830	45.0		3.1761702	1.267422e+00	0.18893617	3.3651064
## 112	4.3863830	45.0		3.1761702	1.267422e+00	0.18893617	3.3651064
## 113	4.3863830	45.0		3.1761702	1.267422e+00	0.18893617	3.3651064
##	PlusIn.N		Y1	Sigma1	n1	PlusMi.Mean	PlusMi.SD
## 1	30		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 2	8	4.70455397		3.14722767	8.0	9.9504406	1.56583475
## 3	8	1.01185943		3.59842642	8.0	9.9504406	1.56583475
## 4	16	0.76595745		4.64590436	16.0	16.5319149	4.42553191
## 5	30		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 6	30		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 7	5	0.14938546		0.19431938	5.0	1.3044171	0.31537746
## 8	30		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 9	30		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

## 10	7	0.24669821	0.97449790	7.0	11.7191911	4.22765224
## 11	30	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 12	5	0.05195954	0.65438295	5.0	2.1258271	0.08468907
## 13	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 14	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 15	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 16	5	0.14938546	0.19431938	5.0	1.2385916	0.34106551
## 17	5	0.14938546	0.19431938	5.0	1.3211639	0.34327875
## 18	3	4.20000000	0.58309519	3.0	NA	NA
## 19	3	6.82000000	0.94339811	3.0	NA	NA
## 20	3	4.20000000	0.58309519	3.0	NA	NA
## 21	3	6.82000000	0.94339811	3.0	NA	NA
## 22	16	-1.64620939	4.97195670	16.0	3.1046931	1.55956679
## 23	20	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 24	5	0.04997071	0.23478075	5.0	2.1462428	0.23565561
## 25	45	NA	NA	45.0	3.2374468	1.30167702
## 26	45	NA	NA	45.0	4.9480851	1.26742236
## 27	45	NA	NA	45.0	4.7336170	1.23316770
## 29	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 30	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 31	10	-1.90000000	51.24548761	10.0	NA	NA
## 32	5	0.01851852	0.20120995	5.0	1.0487654	0.26225489
## 33	5	0.01851852	0.20120995	5.0	1.0734568	0.07591589
## 34	5	0.01851852	0.20120995	5.0	1.1537037	0.08971878
## 35	5	0.56972777	0.17027882	5.0	1.0409742	0.21079265
## 36	5	0.56972777	0.17027882	5.0	1.1352436	0.10763880
## 37	5	0.56972777	0.17027882	5.0	1.2074499	0.17042810
## 38	12	8.88554217	61.69554131	12.0	84.6385542	45.90978044
## 39	10	-57.10000000	59.51890456	10.0	NA	NA
## 40	10	9.60000000	73.36824926	10.0	NA	NA
## 41	10	663.00000000	102.54023600	10.0	NA	NA
## 42	12	15.96385542	71.41222622	12.0	114.6084337	62.08254401
## 43	12	16.86746988	52.48488574	12.0	116.8674699	62.60424606
## 44	16	3.06864989	1.51652554	16.0	1.1304348	1.12585812
## 45	10	18.24285367	277.01896616	10.0	2808.3556726	166.45191939
## 46	10	67.56718791	376.93798421	10.0	1503.3873650	219.42715810
## 47	10	90.37422336	156.87876896	10.0	2990.5186926	82.38713134
## 48	10	300.29401065	529.89685632	10.0	2668.9817882	530.43417403
## 49	30	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 50	10	0.13759531	0.16058526	10.0	1.0597260	0.16244829
## 51	10	0.13759531	0.16058526	10.0	0.9833236	0.12445869
## 52	9	NA	NA	9.0	NA	NA
## 53	9	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 54	9	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 55	3	NA	NA	3.0	4.1781513	0.05822020
## 56	3	NA	NA	3.0	4.1075630	0.06404221
## 57	7	0.24669821	0.97449790	7.0	37.5326690	12.62285820
## 58	7	0.24669821	0.97449790	7.0	32.4063353	12.22183886
## 59	10	0.13759531	0.16058526	10.0	0.8581577	0.28286532
## 60	15	91.53132251	111.22062710	15.0	98.4918794	68.74320789
## 61	8	3.06554721	4.15602221	8.0	9.9504406	1.56583475
## 62	16	0.01368301	2.40276154	16.0	3.7263398	1.97035348
## 63	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 64	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

## 65	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 66	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 67	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 68	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 69	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 70	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 71	4	3.20000000	5.55697760	4.0	27.5000000	5.00000000
## 72	4	3.20000000	5.55697760	4.0	24.7000000	0.60000000
## 73	4	3.20000000	5.55697760	4.0	20.8000000	1.20000000
## 74	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 75	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 76	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 77	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 78	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 79	5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 80	15	3.44661096	13.51478909	15.0	25.4930362	5.86881042
## 81	16	3.22187171	4.45906787	16.0	3.7760252	1.81703470
## 82	4	-0.01640514	0.02371009	4.0	0.3223966	0.01997147
## 83	4	-0.23921569	0.14042404	4.0	1.0718954	0.19869281
## 84	10	NA	NA	10.0	1.3558801	0.13125518
## 85	8	-1.03467562	4.34346325	8.0	28.9373602	4.27852349
## 86	6	0.18057744	0.51326636	5.0	1.4771948	0.56046378
## 87	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 88	6	94.86060271	82.19049146	6.0	340.0930276	85.01887729
## 89	26	0.77391032	0.95204712	26.0	4.2484083	0.83928404
## 90	72	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 91	7	-1.48500000	9.79217383	7.0	23.9950000	5.09500000
## 92	8	2.55421531	2.90010008	7.5	10.3307263	1.27422810
## 93	16	14.19540230	7.91018415	16.0	22.7011494	6.66666667
## 94	34	NA	NA	34.0	0.3932111	0.24384700
## 95	3	NA	NA	3.0	3.8285714	0.09897433
## 96	16	1.66666667	2.80610474	16.0	11.6551724	4.90421456
## 97	8	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 98	8	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 100	5	-0.15286300	0.48206875	5.0	2.4925257	0.20595405
## 101	16	1.76470588	3.08530416	16.0	16.7226891	4.36974790
## 102	3	4.20000000	0.58309519	3.0	NA	NA
## 103	3	6.82000000	0.94339811	3.0	NA	NA
## 104	4	1.90000000	6.87313611	4.0	29.8000000	7.20000000
## 105	4	50.00000000	6.87313611	4.0	28.3000000	7.60000000
## 106	4	50.00000000	6.87313611	4.0	23.5000000	8.20000000
## 107	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 108	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 109	8	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 110	8	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
## 111	45	NA	NA	45.0	3.2374468	1.30167702
## 112	45	NA	NA	45.0	4.9480851	1.26742236
## 113	45	NA	NA	45.0	4.7336170	1.23316770
##	PlusMi.SE	PlusMi.SE2B	PlusMi.N	InMi.Mean	InMi.SD	InMi.SE
## 1	NA	NA	NA	3.3193277	1.61094870	0.29411765
## 2	0.55360618	10.5040468	8	9.9887450	3.54717669	1.25411635
## 3	0.55360618	10.5040468	8	10.2259396	1.33837305	0.47318633
## 4	1.10638298	17.6382979	16	22.3191489	5.78723404	1.44680851
## 5	NA	NA	NA	4.4747899	3.10682963	0.56722689

## 6	NA	NA	NA	1.4075630	1.15067764	0.21008403
## 7	0.14104109	0.9634552	5	0.7257565	0.39660828	0.17736862
## 8	NA	NA	NA	3.2983193	2.53149081	0.46218487
## 9	NA	NA	NA	5.0630252	4.02737175	0.73529412
## 10	1.59790235	13.3170935	7	8.9773800	3.31205749	1.25184006
## 11	NA	NA	NA	3.1512605	2.41642305	0.44117647
## 12	NA	NA	5	2.2121211	0.17255023	NA
## 13	NA	NA	NA	6.8695652	2.36106557	1.05590062
## 14	NA	NA	NA	4.0993789	0.73609691	0.32919255
## 15	NA	NA	NA	4.2732919	1.23608727	0.55279503
## 16	0.15252913	1.5905316	5	0.7071850	0.24356255	0.10892448
## 17	0.15351893	1.1877076	5	1.1821218	0.14380304	0.06431067
## 18	NA	NA	NA	21.0300000	0.19000000	NA
## 19	NA	NA	NA	21.6500000	0.50000000	NA
## 20	NA	NA	NA	21.8200000	0.70000000	NA
## 21	NA	NA	NA	23.2100000	0.20000000	NA
## 22	0.38989170	3.4945848	16	6.0288809	2.68592058	0.67148014
## 23	NA	NA	NA	1.5100000	0.40249224	0.09000000
## 24	NA	NA	5	2.7072215	0.40071880	NA
## 25	0.19404255	3.4314894	45	2.0425532	1.33593168	0.19914894
## 26	0.18893617	5.1370213	45	3.3855319	1.26742236	0.18893617
## 27	0.18382979	4.9174468	45	3.6204255	1.23316770	0.18382979
## 29	NA	NA	NA	2217.6878368	214.81928413	96.07010442
## 30	NA	NA	NA	2325.2754758	107.51816843	48.08358669
## 31	NA	NA	NA	183.6000000	38.57978745	12.20000000
## 32	0.11728395	1.1660494	5	1.0024691	0.09662022	0.04320988
## 33	0.03395062	1.1074074	5	0.8111111	0.22774766	0.10185185
## 34	0.04012346	1.1938272	5	1.0858025	0.19324044	0.08641975
## 35	0.09426934	1.1352436	5	0.5021033	0.19239591	0.08604207
## 36	0.04813754	1.1833811	5	0.5021033	0.05130557	0.02294455
## 37	0.07621777	1.2836676	5	0.3912046	0.07695836	0.03441683
## 38	13.25301205	97.8915663	12	68.3734940	37.56254763	10.84337349
## 39	NA	NA	NA	537.9000000	92.02227991	29.10000000
## 40	NA	NA	NA	168.7000000	29.09295447	9.20000000
## 41	NA	NA	NA	830.8000000	86.33018012	27.30000000
## 42	17.92168675	132.5301205	12	87.5000000	46.43148249	13.40361446
## 43	18.07228916	134.9397590	12	82.0783132	44.34467429	12.80120482
## 44	0.28146453	1.4118993	16	1.3020595	1.51029748	0.37757437
## 45	52.63671863	2860.9923912	10	2740.0401956	126.44237987	39.98459131
## 46	69.38896001	1572.7763248	10	1344.6430957	299.65550555	94.75939110
## 47	26.05309849	3016.5717911	10	2881.1563388	218.54899137	69.11125931
## 48	167.73801382	2836.7198021	10	2073.5984868	449.11839124	142.02370559
## 49	NA	NA	NA	5.5800000	1.25976188	0.23000000
## 50	0.05137066	1.1110967	10	0.6910192	0.22494390	0.07113351
## 51	0.03935729	1.0226809	10	0.9161600	0.13839424	0.04376410
## 52	NA	NA	NA	1.8700000	0.39000000	0.13000000
## 53	NA	NA	NA	2.4000000	0.39000000	0.13000000
## 54	NA	NA	NA	2.2100000	0.27000000	0.09000000
## 55	0.03361344	4.2117647	3	3.9092437	0.04075414	0.02352941
## 56	0.03697479	4.1445378	3	3.5126050	0.07568625	0.04369748
## 57	4.77099195	42.3036610	7	22.5093112	7.75305307	2.93037862
## 58	4.61942089	37.0257562	7	21.6095473	7.79555944	2.94644452
## 59	0.08944987	0.9476076	10	0.7499336	0.21991776	0.06954410
## 60	17.74941995	116.2412993	15	19.1415313	21.56649659	5.56844548

## 61	0.55360618	10.5040468	8	9.9087090	2.77626540	0.98155805
## 62	0.49258837	4.2189282	16	3.4663626	1.47776511	0.36944128
## 63	NA	NA	NA	3342.7034599	161.02942644	72.01454879
## 64	NA	NA	NA	3005.8613070	41.60230537	18.60511656
## 65	NA	NA	NA	5.1801242	0.91664899	0.40993789
## 66	NA	NA	NA	5.6397516	2.83327868	1.26708074
## 67	NA	NA	NA	3.2546584	0.80554002	0.36024845
## 68	NA	NA	NA	11.6770186	2.83327868	1.26708074
## 69	NA	NA	NA	3.8757764	1.31941899	0.59006211
## 70	NA	NA	NA	5.1180124	1.31941899	0.59006211
## 71	2.50000000	NA	4	26.2000000	4.60000000	2.30000000
## 72	0.30000000	NA	4	24.5000000	6.00000000	3.00000000
## 73	0.60000000	NA	4	20.4000000	4.00000000	2.00000000
## 74	NA	NA	NA	6.1739130	1.51385969	0.67701863
## 75	NA	NA	NA	2.7950311	0.79165140	0.35403727
## 76	NA	NA	NA	2.9068323	1.05553519	0.47204969
## 77	NA	NA	NA	6.7329193	0.83331726	0.37267081
## 78	NA	NA	NA	3.8260870	1.26386451	0.56521739
## 79	NA	NA	NA	2.7080745	0.99998071	0.44720497
## 80	1.51532033	27.0083565	15	12.8950789	8.28537941	2.13927577
## 81	0.45425868	4.2302839	16	1.3701367	0.77392219	0.19348055
## 82	NA	0.3423680	4	0.3766048	0.03209700	NA
## 83	0.09934640	1.1712418	4	1.2339869	0.13594771	0.06797386
## 84	0.04150653	1.3973866	10	1.0699462	0.17136093	0.05418908
## 85	NA	33.2158837	8	24.5749441	4.11073826	NA
## 86	0.21183540	1.6890302	7	1.1796792	0.45762960	0.17296773
## 87	NA	NA	NA	70.2767528	8.91590729	5.14760148
## 88	34.70881132	374.8018389	6	258.6452268	62.56810429	25.54332162
## 89	0.16459714	4.4130054	26	3.5008976	0.74085868	0.14529434
## 90	NA	NA	NA	2.6122449	1.15446005	0.13605442
## 91	NA	NA	8	24.8450000	4.05500000	NA
## 92	NA	NA	9	9.1001165	1.90107979	NA
## 93	1.66666667	24.3678161	16	14.9425287	3.67816092	0.91954023
## 94	0.04181942	0.4350306	34	0.4469790	0.23434647	0.04019009
## 95	0.05714286	3.8857143	3	3.0184874	0.06986423	0.04033613
## 96	1.22605364	12.8812261	16	8.5229885	4.02298851	1.00574713
## 97	NA	NA	NA	3151.0000000	172.90175010	61.13000000
## 98	NA	NA	NA	3162.0000000	201.72342250	71.32000000
## 100	NA	NA	5	2.1952484	0.35389360	NA
## 101	1.09243698	17.8151260	16	22.3949580	4.20168067	1.05042017
## 102	NA	NA	NA	20.4400000	0.50000000	NA
## 103	NA	NA	NA	17.8300000	0.50000000	NA
## 104	3.60000000	NA	4	25.2000000	1.40000000	0.70000000
## 105	3.80000000	NA	4	24.4000000	1.60000000	0.80000000
## 106	4.10000000	NA	4	21.7000000	4.40000000	2.20000000
## 107	NA	NA	NA	6.5700000	2.08000000	1.04000000
## 108	NA	NA	NA	21.5600000	2.56000000	1.28000000
## 109	NA	NA	NA	3038.0000000	112.42997820	39.75000000
## 110	NA	NA	NA	3016.0000000	100.86171130	35.66000000
## 111	0.19404255	3.4314894	45	3.2629787	1.30167702	0.19404255
## 112	0.18893617	5.1370213	45	3.3548936	1.26742236	0.18893617
## 113	0.18382979	4.9174468	45	3.3089362	1.26742236	0.18893617
##	InMi.SE2B	InMi.N	Y2	Sigma2	n2	
## 1	3.6134454	30	NA	NA	NA	

## 2	11.2428614	8	-0.03830438	3.88946916	8
## 3	10.6991260	8	-0.27549898	2.07530321	8
## 4	23.7659574	16	-5.78723404	7.28542453	16
## 5	5.0420168	30	NA	NA	NA
## 6	1.6176471	30	NA	NA	NA
## 7	0.5730897	5	0.57866051	0.50871935	5
## 8	3.7605042	30	NA	NA	NA
## 9	5.7983193	30	NA	NA	NA
## 10	10.2292200	7	NA	NA	7
## 11	3.5924370	30	NA	NA	NA
## 12	NA	5	-0.08629398	0.19237113	5
## 13	8.9813665	5	NA	NA	NA
## 14	4.7577640	5	NA	NA	NA
## 15	5.3788820	5	NA	NA	NA
## 16	0.6063123	5	0.53140654	0.42218644	5
## 17	0.8970100	5	0.13904214	0.37219349	5
## 18	NA	3	NA	NA	3
## 19	NA	3	NA	NA	3
## 20	NA	3	NA	NA	3
## 21	NA	3	NA	NA	3
## 22	6.7003610	16	-2.92418773	3.10586830	16
## 23	NA	20	NA	NA	NA
## 24	NA	5	-0.56097869	0.47151019	5
## 25	2.2417021	45	NA	NA	NA
## 26	3.5744681	45	NA	NA	NA
## 27	3.8042553	45	NA	NA	NA
## 29	2313.7579413	5	NA	NA	NA
## 30	2373.3590626	5	NA	NA	NA
## 31	NA	10	NA	NA	10
## 32	1.0456790	5	0.04629630	0.27948720	5
## 33	0.9129630	5	0.26234568	0.24006712	5
## 34	1.1722222	5	0.06790124	0.21305241	5
## 35	0.5881453	5	0.53887096	0.28539399	5
## 36	0.5250478	5	0.63314030	0.11924082	5
## 37	0.4256214	5	0.81624527	0.18699820	5
## 38	79.2168675	12	16.26506024	59.31823434	12
## 39	NA	10	NA	NA	10
## 40	NA	10	NA	NA	10
## 41	NA	10	NA	NA	10
## 42	100.9036145	12	27.10843373	77.52499492	12
## 43	94.8795181	12	34.78915663	76.71858811	12
## 44	1.6796339	16	-0.17162471	1.88376087	16
## 45	2780.0247871	10	68.31547685	209.17798823	10
## 46	1439.4024866	10	158.74426921	371.71792219	10
## 47	2950.2675979	10	109.36235390	233.65717154	10
## 48	2215.6221925	10	595.38330132	695.05087287	10
## 49	NA	30	NA	NA	NA
## 50	0.7621527	10	0.36870682	0.27784231	10
## 51	0.9599241	10	0.06716366	0.18975125	10
## 52	NA	9	NA	NA	NA
## 53	NA	9	NA	NA	NA
## 54	NA	9	NA	NA	NA
## 55	3.9327731	3	NA	NA	3
## 56	3.5563025	3	NA	NA	NA

## 57	25.4396898	7	NA	14.81372273	7
## 58	24.5559918	7	NA	NA	7
## 59	0.8194777	10	0.10822414	0.35836079	10
## 60	24.7099768	15	79.35034803	72.04680705	15
## 61	10.8902670	8	0.04173165	3.22750657	8
## 62	3.8358039	16	0.25997719	2.46294185	16
## 63	3414.7180099	5	NA	NA	NA
## 64	3024.4664235	5	NA	NA	NA
## 65	6.0000000	5	NA	NA	NA
## 66	8.1739130	5	NA	NA	NA
## 67	3.9751553	5	NA	NA	NA
## 68	14.2111801	5	NA	NA	NA
## 69	5.0559006	5	NA	NA	NA
## 70	6.2981366	5	NA	NA	NA
## 71	NA	4	1.30000000	6.79411510	4
## 72	NA	4	0.20000000	6.02992537	4
## 73	NA	4	0.40000000	4.17612260	4
## 74	7.5279503	5	NA	NA	NA
## 75	3.5031056	5	NA	NA	NA
## 76	3.8509317	5	NA	NA	NA
## 77	7.4782609	5	NA	NA	NA
## 78	4.9565217	5	NA	NA	NA
## 79	3.6024845	5	NA	NA	NA
## 80	15.0343547	15	12.59795729	10.15334663	15
## 81	1.5636172	16	2.40588854	1.97498624	16
## 82	0.4087019	4	-0.05420827	0.03780314	4
## 83	1.3019608	4	-0.16209150	0.24075011	4
## 84	1.1241353	10	NA	NA	10
## 85	28.6856823	8	4.36241611	5.93329017	8
## 86	1.3526470	7	0.29751554	0.72482213	7
## 87	75.4243542	3	NA	NA	NA
## 88	284.1885484	6	81.44780077	105.59490592	6
## 89	3.6461919	26	0.74751067	1.12148191	26
## 90	2.7482993	72	NA	NA	NA
## 91	NA	8	-0.85000000	6.54020408	8
## 92	NA	8	1.23060972	2.29696823	8
## 93	15.8620690	16	7.75862069	7.61402076	16
## 94	0.4871690	34	NA	NA	34
## 95	3.0588235	3	NA	NA	3
## 96	9.5287356	16	3.13218391	6.34316616	16
## 97	NA	8	NA	NA	NA
## 98	NA	8	NA	NA	NA
## 100	NA	5	0.29727730	0.40948252	5
## 101	23.4453781	16	-5.67226891	6.06208027	16
## 102	NA	3	NA	NA	3
## 103	NA	3	NA	NA	3
## 104	NA	4	4.60000000	7.33484833	4
## 105	NA	4	3.90000000	7.76659514	4
## 106	NA	4	1.80000000	9.30591210	4
## 107	NA	4	NA	NA	NA
## 108	NA	4	NA	NA	NA
## 109	NA	8	NA	NA	NA
## 110	NA	8	NA	NA	NA
## 111	3.4570213	45	NA	NA	NA

## 112	3.5438298	45	NA	NA NA
## 113	3.4978723	45	NA	NA NA
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57 left reproductive biomass off on this study because I believe it's included in total biomass
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SHADEHOUSE

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Not sure if this counts as yield or weight, as it's yield but in kg/ha

##	yi	vi
## 1	-1.4891	0.0851
## 2	1.2101	0.1812
## 3	0.1241	0.1523
## 4	3.4531	0.3113
## 5	-0.9738	0.0746
## 6	-0.1592	0.0669
## 7	-0.1860	0.2642
## 8	-0.8634	0.0729
## 9	-0.7100	0.0709
## 10	2.9361	0.5936
## 11	0.1010	0.0668
## 12	-0.7866	0.2722
## 13	-0.2554	0.4033
## 14	-1.9436	0.5889
## 15	-1.6855	0.5420
## 16	-0.3098	0.2608
## 17	1.2159	0.3779
## 18	14.8393	19.0172
## 19	11.4895	11.6675
## 20	8.0897	6.1203
## 21	18.3552	28.7429
## 22	-1.7077	0.1706
## 23	1.2776	0.1204
## 24	1.2157	0.2966
## 25	-1.0148	0.0502
## 26	0.0080	0.0444
## 27	0.1943	0.0447
## 29	0.6415	0.2086
## 30	0.6211	0.2235
## 31	0.0578	0.2001
## 32	-0.2192	0.4024
## 33	-1.0067	0.4507
## 34	0.2434	0.4030
## 35	0.6032	0.4182
## 36	1.0495	0.4551
## 37	-0.0343	0.4001
## 38	-0.1807	0.1673
## 39	2.6468	0.3751
## 40	-4.7557	0.7654
## 41	7.2898	1.5285
## 42	0.0845	0.1668
## 43	0.5839	0.1738
## 44	0.1924	0.1256
## 45	0.3220	0.0985
## 46	0.4249	0.0986
## 47	0.7904	0.1071
## 48	0.9571	0.1080

```
## 49  2.5076  0.1191
## 50 -0.5730  0.1268
## 51  0.2851  0.1291
## 52 -0.7940  0.2397
## 53  0.7646  0.2385
## 54  0.2610  0.2241
## 55 22.1694 41.6236
## 56 11.1247 10.9799
## 57  3.5751  0.7422
## 58  3.4035  0.6994
## 59 -0.5352  0.1269
## 60 -1.3855  0.1653
## 61  0.5713  0.1582
## 62  0.9064  0.1378
## 63  0.7172  0.2158
## 64  0.7747  0.2055
## 65 -0.1339  0.4009
## 66  0.0815  0.4003
## 67 -1.2499  0.4781
## 68  1.4049  0.4987
## 69 -1.5319  0.5173
## 70 -0.9944  0.4494
## 71  1.6999  0.6806
## 72  1.1990  0.5899
## 73  0.6685  0.5279
## 74  1.7800  0.5584
## 75 -1.4922  0.5113
## 76 -1.0902  0.4594
## 77  3.1691  0.9022
## 78  0.2374  0.4028
## 79 -0.7453  0.4278
## 80  0.2980  0.1348
## 81  0.1527  0.1254
## 82  4.0955  1.5483
## 83  2.7165  0.9612
## 84  1.7066  0.2728
## 85  1.0905  0.2872
## 86  1.0191  0.2161
## 87  0.7384  0.7121
## 88  1.2700  0.2438
## 89  0.6673  0.0494
## 90 -0.0484  0.0278
## 91  1.0164  0.1857
## 92  1.7166  0.2386
## 93 -0.7535  0.1339
## 94  0.4362  0.0602
## 95  5.3421  3.0448
## 96  1.1598  0.1460
## 97  0.3455  0.2537
## 98  0.3730  0.2543
## 100 0.1600  0.2514
## 101 5.6939  0.6316
## 102 7.8954  5.8615
## 103 5.3937  3.0910
```

```
## 104 5.4979 2.3891
## 105 4.4923 1.7613
## 106 1.1434 0.5817
## 107 0.3031 0.5057
## 108 3.8718 1.4369
## 109 -0.1942 0.2512
## 110 -0.4112 0.2553
## 111 0.0670 0.0445
## 112 0.1398 0.0446
## 113 0.1039 0.0445
```

```
#below used to be relevant when this moderator was categorical
```

```
# RP.predict <- as.data.frame(predict(RP.mod, newmods = rbind(c(0), c(1))))
# RP.predict$level <- sort(unique(es.agg.RP$RegrowthPeriod))
# RP.predict$n <- 0
# for (i in 1:length(RP.predict$level)) {
#   RP.predict$n[i] <- nrow(es.agg.RP[which(es.agg.RP$RegrowthPeriod == RP.predict$level[i]),])
# } #tally up the number of effect sizes representing each level of the moderator
# RP.predict$pval <- RP.mod$QMp
# RP.predict$QM <- RP.mod$QM
# RP.predict$moderator <- "Regrowth period"
```

```
#drop unknowns
```

```
es.agg.MS <- es.agg[-which(es.agg$MiSource=="Unknown"),]
es.agg.MS$MiSource[es.agg.MS$MiSource == "Academic stock"] <- "Lab stock"
es.agg.MS <- es.agg.MS[-which(es.agg.MS$MiSource=="Mixed"),] #had to drop "Mixed" as it was represented
```

```
#create model with a single moderator: root or shoot herbivory
```

```
MS.mod <- rma.mv(yi, vi, random = ~1|Citation/Exp/Rep.Name, mods = ~MiSource,
                data = es.agg.MS)
MS.mod #omnibus test says significant (p = 0.003)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 95; method: REML)
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim      sqrt  nlvls  fixed      factor
## sigma^2.1 1.3291  1.1529   28    no      Citation
## sigma^2.2 1.9095  1.3818   61    no      Citation/Exp
## sigma^2.3 0.3217  0.5672   95    no      Citation/Exp/Rep.Name
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 92) = 652.6780, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):
## QM(df = 2) = 6.7041, p-val = 0.0350
##
## Model Results:
##
##      estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt          0.6029  0.3953  1.5253  0.1272  -0.1718  1.3777
```

```
## MiSourceField isolate -0.0061 0.6646 -0.0091 0.9927 -1.3087 1.2965
## MiSourceLab stock 2.0192 0.7984 2.5290 0.0114 0.4544 3.5841 *
##
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

*#the intercept gives us the estimated (average) effect size associated with the alphabetically first mo
#to find the estimates for the other levels, we must...*

```
ms.predict <- as.data.frame(predict(MS.mod, newmods = rbind(c(0,0), c(1,0), c(0,1))))
ms.predict$level <- sort(unique(es.agg.MS$MiSource))
ms.predict$n <- 0
for (i in 1:length(ms.predict$level)) {
  ms.predict$n[i] <- nrow(es.agg.MS[which(es.agg.MS$MiSource == ms.predict$level[i]),])
} #tally up the number of effect sizes representing each level of the moderator
ms.predict$pval <- MS.mod$QMp
ms.predict$QM <- MS.mod$QM
ms.predict$moderator <- "Innoculant source"
```

#visualize the spread of species richness here, so we can figure out how to group/categorize community

```
es.agg.CCRichness <- es.agg[-which(es.agg$CoCoSppRichness=="Unknown"),] #remove "Unknown"
es.agg.CCRichness$CoCoSppRichness[es.agg.CCRichness$CoCoSppRichness=="Max"] <- 5
unique(es.agg.CCRichness$CoCoSppRichness)
```

```
## [1] "4" "5" "1" "2" "3"
```

```
ggplot(es.agg.CCRichness, aes(x = as.numeric(CoCoSppRichness))) +
  geom_histogram() + theme_bw()
```

```
## 'stat_bin()' using 'bins = 30'. Pick better value with 'binwidth'.
```



```

es.agg.CC <- es.agg[-which(es.agg$CoCoSimple=="Unknown"),]

#create model with a single moderator: root or shoot herbivory
CC.mod <- rma.mv(yi, vi, random = ~1|Citation/Exp/Rep.Name, mods = ~CoCoSimple,
                data = es.agg.CC)
CC.mod #omnibus test says significant (p < 0.001)

```

```

##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 109; method: REML)
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim      sqrt  nlvls  fixed      factor
## sigma^2.1  1.8412  1.3569   33    no      Citation
## sigma^2.2  2.2142  1.4880   68    no      Citation/Exp
## sigma^2.3  0.1356  0.3682  109    no      Citation/Exp/Rep.Name
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 106) = 674.4250, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):
## QM(df = 2) = 17.0623, p-val = 0.0002
##
## Model Results:
##

```

```

##              estimate      se    zval    pval    ci.lb    ci.ub
## intrcpt          0.3184  0.3786  0.8409  0.4004  -0.4237  1.0604
## CoCoSimpleSingle    1.4526  0.3692  3.9340 <.0001   0.7289  2.1763
## CoCoSimpleSmall consortia  1.7625  0.4934  3.5726  0.0004   0.7956  2.7295
##
## intrcpt
## CoCoSimpleSingle      ***
## CoCoSimpleSmall consortia ***
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

*#the intercept gives us the estimated (average) effect size associated with the alphabetically first mo
#to find the estimates for the other levels, we must...*

```

cc.predict <- as.data.frame(predict(CC.mod, newmods = rbind(c(0,0), c(1,0), c(0,1))))
cc.predict$level <- sort(unique(es.agg.CC$CoCoSimple))
mfg.predict$n <- 0
for (i in 1:length(cc.predict$level)) {
  cc.predict$n[i] <- nrow(es.agg.CC[which(es.agg.CC$CoCoSimple == cc.predict$level[i]),])
} #tally up the number of effect sizes representing each level of the moderator
cc.predict$pval <- CC.mod$QMp
cc.predict$QM <- CC.mod$QM
cc.predict$moderator <- "Total soil community diversity"

```

```

es.agg$Environ[es.agg$Environ == "Field"] <- "Other field"
#create model with a single moderator: root or shoot herbivory
E.mod <- rma.mv(yi, vi, random = ~1|Citation/Exp/Rep.Name, mods = ~Environ,
               data = es.agg)
E.mod #omnibus test says NS (p = 0.87)

```

```

##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 113; method: REML)
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed      factor
## sigma^2.1 0.9997 0.9999   35    no      Citation
## sigma^2.2 2.0419 1.4290   72    no      Citation/Exp
## sigma^2.3 0.3143 0.5606  113    no      Citation/Exp/Rep.Name
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 108) = 725.5660, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:5):
## QM(df = 4) = 1.2130, p-val = 0.8759
##
## Model Results:
##
##              estimate      se    zval    pval    ci.lb    ci.ub
## intrcpt          0.5873  1.0091  0.5820  0.5606  -1.3905  2.5650
## EnvironExperimental station  0.7716  1.1091  0.6957  0.4866  -1.4022  2.9455
## EnvironGreenhouse    0.3159  1.0717  0.2947  0.7682  -1.7846  2.4163

```

```

## EnvironGrowth chamber          1.0009  1.3140  0.7617  0.4462 -1.5745  3.5763
## EnvironOther field             0.2007  1.2705  0.1580  0.8745 -2.2894  2.6908
##
## intrcpt
## EnvironExperimental station
## EnvironGreenhouse
## EnvironGrowth chamber
## EnvironOther field
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

*#the intercept gives us the estimated (average) effect size associated with the alphabetically first moderator
#to find the estimates for the other levels, we must...*

```

e.predict <- as.data.frame(predict(E.mod, newmods = rbind(c(0,0,0,0), c(1,0,0,0), c(0,1,0,0), c(0,0,1,0), c(0,0,0,1))))
e.predict$level <- sort(unique(es.agg$Environ))
e.predict$n <- 0
for (i in 1:length(e.predict$level)) {
  e.predict$n[i] <- nrow(es.agg[which(es.agg$Environ == e.predict$level[i]),])
} #tally up the number of effect sizes representing each level of the moderator
e.predict$pval <- E.mod$QMp
e.predict$QM <- E.mod$QM
e.predict$moderator <- "Experimental environment"

```

```

pred2plot <- rbind(
  ifg.predict, rsh.predict, PFG.predict,
  mfg.predict, ms.predict, e.predict, cc.predict, if.predict)
#add grand mean effect size info; a bit clunky, but the only way I could do it without most columns being NA
#ah for future me: rbind and cbind return matrices, which can not have mixed character and numeric columns
grand.mean <- c(main.model$b[1], main.model$se, main.model$ci.lb, main.model$ci.ub,
  NA, NA, NA, nrow(es.agg), main.model$pval, NA, 66)
pred2plot <- rbind(pred2plot, grand.mean)
pred2plot$moderator[nrow(pred2plot)] <- "Grand mean effect size"

```

```

#round the p values
pred2plot$pval <- round(pred2plot$pval, 3)

```

```

#create a data frame for a later geom_text object
p.annotations <- data.frame(moderator = unique(pred2plot$moderator), pval = 0)

```

```

for (i in 1:nrow(p.annotations)) {
  j <- p.annotations$moderator[i]
  p.annotations$pval[i] <- pred2plot[which(pred2plot$moderator == j),]$pval[1]
}

```

```

p.annotations$pval[nrow(p.annotations)] <- round(main.model$pval, 3)

```

```

# pred2plot.ordered <- pred2plot %>%
#   ungroup() %>%
#   arrange(moderator, pred) %>%
#   mutate(order = row_number())

```

```

hedges.d.fig <- ggplot(pred2plot, aes(x = pred, y = level)) +

```

```

geom_vline(xintercept = 0, linetype = "dashed", color = "black") +
geom_vline(xintercept = main.model$b, linetype = "dashed", color = "red") +
geom_point(size = 2) + geom_text(aes(group = level, x = ci.ub,
    label = paste(" (", n, ")")),
    position = position_dodge(width = 1),
    hjust = 0, vjust = 0.5, size = 2) +
geom_text(data = p.annotations,
    aes(group = moderator, label = paste("p = ", pval), x = -1.5,
    y = .5), hjust = "right", vjust = "bottom", size = 2) +
geom_errorbar(aes(xmin = ci.lb, xmax = ci.ub, width = 0)) +
labs(x = expression(paste("Hedges' ", italic("d"))), y = element_blank()) +
facet_wrap(~factor(moderator, levels = c("Herbivore feeding guild",
    "Site of herbivore feeding", "Effect of microbe(s) on herbivore fitness",
    "Plant cultivation status",
    "Microbial inoculant functional guild", "Innoculant source",
    "Total soil community diversity", "Experimental environment",
    "Grand mean effect size")), ncol = 2, nrow = 5, scales = "free_y",
    strip.position = "top") +
theme_bw() +
theme(strip.background = element_blank(), strip.text = element_text(face = "bold", size = 10)) +
xlim(-3.5, 5.5)
hedges.d.fig

```



```

#setwd("/Users/emilytronson/OneDrive - purdue.edu/Tronson Meeting Files/Literature Review")
#ggsave(filename = "hedges-d2.pdf", plot = hedges.d.fig, height = 7, width = 8)

```

Meta-analysis DUE-DILIGENCE [Fail-safe N; sensitivity analysis]

Fail-safe N: How many unpublished observations out there with null results are needed to make our grand mean effect size non-significant when added to our pool of observations?

```
fsn(yi, vi, data = es.agg)
```

```
##  
## Fail-safe N Calculation Using the Rosenthal Approach  
##  
## Observed Significance Level: <.0001  
## Target Significance Level: 0.05  
##  
## Fail-safe N: 4730
```

```
#fsn = 4730  
#our average paper-to-observation ratio  
nrow(es.agg)/length(unique(es.agg$Citation))
```

```
## [1] 3.228571
```

```
4730/3.2 # = 1478 unpublished papers
```

```
## [1] 1478.125
```

```
#get color palette  
cols <- colors()[seq(1, length(colors()), 17)][c(2:12, 16:39)]  
cols <- cols[as.numeric(factor(es.agg$Citation))]  
  
funnel.plot <- funnel(main.model, col = cols) #original model; enormous; difficult to see
```



```
#zoom in?  
funnel.zoomed <- funnel(main.model, ylim = c(2, 0), col = cols)
```



```
#egger's test -esque test of funnel plot asymmetry
eggers.test <- rma.mv(yi, vi, random = ~ 1|Citation/Exp/Rep.Name, mods = ~vi,
                    data = es.agg)
eggers.test #significant moderator at p <0.0001 --> there is asymmetry in our funnel plot
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 113; method: REML)
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed      factor
## sigma^2.1 0.1205 0.3472   35    no      Citation
## sigma^2.2 1.1482 1.0715   72    no      Citation/Exp
## sigma^2.3 0.2965 0.5445  113    no      Citation/Exp/Rep.Name
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 111) = 598.0218, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficient 2):
## QM(df = 1) = 67.6575, p-val < .0001
##
## Model Results:
##
##      estimate    se    zval    pval    ci.lb    ci.ub
## intrcpt    0.4286 0.1740  2.4626 0.0138  0.0875  0.7697 *
```

```
## vi          0.7983  0.0971  8.2254  <.0001  0.6081  0.9885  ***
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
cd <- cooks.distance(main.model, cluster = Citation)
cd[cd > 0.5] #Batool et al. 2022 is the only paper with a Cook's distance greater than 0.5
```

```
## Batool et al. 2022
##          1.174139
```

```
#empty dataframe for filling in the upcoming for loop
sensi <- data.frame(MissingStudy = character(),
                    GMES = numeric(),
                    p = numeric(),
                    ci.upper = numeric(),
                    ci.lower = numeric())

#build our main model without each of the 35 studies; how consistent are the results?
for (i in 1:length(unique(es.agg$Citation))) {
  d <- unique(es.agg$Citation)[i]
  new.df <- es.agg[-which(es.agg$Citation == d),]
  new.mod <- rma.mv(yi, vi, random = ~ 1|Citation/Exp/Rep.Name,
                  data = new.df)
  sensi[nrow(sensi) + 1,] <- c(d, new.mod$b, new.mod$pval, new.mod$ci.ub,
                              new.mod$ci.lb)
}

#add results from our main model for comparison at the end
sensi[nrow(sensi) + 1,] <- c("None", main.model$b, main.model$pval,
                            main.model$ci.ub, main.model$ci.lb)

sensi$GMES <- as.numeric(sensi$GMES)
sensi$ci.lower <- as.numeric(sensi$ci.lower)
sensi$ci.upper <- as.numeric(sensi$ci.upper)

sensi.plot <- sensi[-which(sensi$MissingStudy=="None"),]

#plot!
sensitivity.analysis <- ggplot(sensi.plot, aes(x = GMES, y = MissingStudy)) +
  geom_blank() +
  annotate(geom = "rect", xmin = as.numeric(main.model$ci.lb),
          xmax = as.numeric(main.model$ci.ub),
          ymin = 0, ymax = 35, fill = "#ffb6c1", alpha = .2) +
  geom_vline(xintercept = 0, linetype = "dashed", color = "black") +
  geom_vline(xintercept = main.model$b, linetype = "dashed", color = "red") +
  geom_point(size = 2) +
  # geom_text(data = p.annotations,
  #           aes(group = moderator, label = paste("p = ", pval), x = -1.5,
  #           y = .5), hjust = "right", vjust = "bottom", size = 2) +
  geom_errorbar(aes(xmin = ci.lower, xmax = ci.upper, width = 0)) +
  labs(x = expression(paste("Hedges' ", italic("d"))), y = element_blank()) +
  theme_bw()
sensitivity.analysis
```



```
#setwd("/Users/emilytronson/OneDrive - purdue.edu/Tronson Meeting Files/Literature Review")
#ggsave(filename = "sensitivity-analysis.pdf", plot = sensitivity.analysis)
```

```
forest(main.model, psize = 1.5, order = "obs", xlim = c(-10,55), slab = Citation)
```



```
viz_rainforest(main.model, study_labels = main.model$data$Citation)
```

```
## Warning: The 'guide' argument in 'scale_*()' cannot be 'FALSE'. This was deprecated in
## ggplot2 3.3.4.
## i Please use "none" instead.
## i The deprecated feature was likely used in the metaviz package.
## Please report the issue at <https://github.com/Mkossmeier/metaviz/issues>.
## This warning is displayed once every 8 hours.
## Call 'lifecycle::last_lifecycle_warnings()' to see where this warning was
## generated.
```


Well, oops, Batool at all has a huge influence on the dataset. Let's rerun moderator analyses to see if this effects any of the moderator results. ### Re-Run WITHOUT BATOOL ET AL.

```
es.nb <- es.agg[-which(es.agg$Citation == "Batool et al. 2022"),]
nrow(es.agg[which(es.agg$Citation == "Batool et al. 2022"),])
```

```
## [1] 6
```

```
main.model.nb <- rma.mv(yi, vi, random = ~ 1|Citation/Exp/Rep.Name,
                        data = es.nb)
summary(main.model.nb)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 107; method: REML)
##
##   logLik  Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -200.9363  401.8726  409.8726  420.5264  410.2686
##
## Variance Components:
##
##      estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed      factor
## sigma^2.1 0.1308 0.3617   34    no      Citation
## sigma^2.2 1.7140 1.3092   70    no      Citation/Exp
## sigma^2.3 0.3230 0.5683  107    no      Citation/Exp/Rep.Name
##
```

```
## Test for Heterogeneity:
## Q(df = 106) = 682.1625, p-val < .0001
##
## Model Results:
##
## estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## 0.7133 0.1945 3.6679 0.0002 0.3321 1.0944 ***
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Microbe source was the only moderator for which p values were substantially changed (i.e., made non-significant).

```
#here is our first moderator with unknown values. I believe we need to drop the rows with MiSource = "U
es.nb.MS <- es.nb[-which(es.nb$MiSource=="Unknown"),]
es.nb.MS$MiSource[es.nb.MS$MiSource == "Academic stock"] <- "Lab stock"
es.nb.MS <- es.nb.MS[-which(es.nb.MS$MiSource=="Mixed"),] #had to drop "Mixed" as it was represented by

#create model with a single moderator: root or shoot herbivory
MS.mod.nb <- rma.mv(yi, vi, random = ~1|Citation/Exp, mods = ~MiSource,
                  data = es.nb.MS)
MS.mod.nb #omnibus test says significant (p = 0.003)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 89; method: REML)
##
## Variance Components:
##
##          estim      sqrt  nlvls  fixed      factor
## sigma^2.1 0.2779 0.5271    27    no      Citation
## sigma^2.2 2.1710 1.4734    59    no  Citation/Exp
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 86) = 593.3882, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 2:3):
## QM(df = 2) = 1.2197, p-val = 0.5434
##
## Model Results:
##
##          estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## intrcpt          0.5361 0.2882 1.8602 0.0629 -0.0288 1.1009 .
## MiSourceField isolate 0.0979 0.4658 0.2101 0.8336 -0.8152 1.0109
## MiSourceLab stock     0.7137 0.6463 1.1044 0.2694 -0.5529 1.9804
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
#the intercept gives us the estimated (average) effect size associated with the alphabetically first mo
#to find the estimates for the other levels, we must...
```

```
ms.predict.nb <- as.data.frame(predict(MS.mod.nb, newmods = rbind(c(0,0), c(1,0), c(0,1))))
```

```

ms.predict.nb$level <- sort(unique(es.nb.MS$MiSource))
ms.predict.nb$n <- 0
for (i in 1:length(ms.predict.nb$level)) {
  ms.predict.nb$n[i] <- nrow(es.nb.MS[which(es.nb.MS$MiSource == ms.predict.nb$level[i]),])
  } #tally up the number of effect sizes representing each level of the moderator
ms.predict.nb$pval <- MS.mod.nb$QMp
ms.predict.nb$QM <- MS.mod.nb$QM
ms.predict.nb$moderator <- "Innoculant source"

```

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW ANALYSES/VISUALIZATIONS

Below is code for summarizing the studies included in our literature review Date file = "tolerance lit review table_working1august.csv"

```

toltab <- read.csv(file = "tolerance lit review table_working1august.csv")

#make these data ordinal
toltab$Microbes.added <- factor(toltab$Microbes.added, order = TRUE,
                               levels = c("1", "2", "3", "4", "5",
                                           "6", "17", "Consortia",
                                           "Community"))

#plot
microbes.added <- ggplot(toltab, aes(x = Microbes.added, fill = "darkgreen")) +
  geom_bar() +
  scale_fill_manual(values = "darkgreen") +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(legend.position = "none", text = element_text(size = 15),
        axis.text.x = element_text(angle = -30, hjust = 0, vjust = 1),
        plot.margin = margin(10,21,10,10)) +
  labs(y = element_blank(), x = "Microbes added")
microbes.added

```



```
nrow(toltab[toltab$Microbes.added=="Community",])
```

```
## [1] 11
```

```
nrow(toltab)
```

```
## [1] 134
```

```
#setwd("/Users/emilytronson/OneDrive - purdue.edu/Tronson Meeting Files/Literature Review")
#ggsave(filename = "microbes.added.pdf", plot = microbes.added, height = 7, width = 9)
```

```
all.papers <- read.csv(file = "all-papers-summary.csv")
```

```
###insect
```

```
#first some aesthetic tweaks for the Hessian fly
```

```
all.papers[all.papers$InFeGu=="Other",]$InFeGu <- "Galling"
```

```
all.papers[all.papers$InFeGu=="Mixed herbivore community",]$InFeGu <- "Mixed community"
```

```
#and for whole-plant herbivory
```

```
all.papers[all.papers$RoShHe=="Mixed",]$RoShHe <- "Whole plant"
```

```
#plot
```

```
insect.mosaic <- all.papers %>% group_by(RoShHe, InFeGu) %>%
```

```
  summarise(count = n()) %>%
```

```
  mutate(cut.count = sum(count),
```

```

    prop = count/sum(count)) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = RoShHe, y = prop, width = cut.count, fill = InFeGu)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", position = "fill", colour = "black") +
  geom_text(aes(label = paste("(", count, ")", sep = "")),
            position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5)) + # if labels are desired
  facet_grid(~RoShHe, scales = "free_x", space = "free_x") +
  scale_fill_manual(values = tetradic("#984d7479")) +
  theme_classic() +
  theme(strip.background = element_blank(),
        strip.text = element_blank(),
        axis.text.y = element_blank(), axis.title.y = element_blank(),
        axis.ticks.y = element_blank(), axis.line.y = element_blank(),
        text = element_text(size = 18))+
  labs(fill = "Insect feeding guild", x = "Site of herbivore feeding")

```

'summarise()' has grouped output by 'RoShHe'. You can override using the
'.groups' argument.


```
insect.mosaic
```



```
###plant
#bin age-at-infestation data; we first need to remove the "Unknowns," then bin, then rbind the Unknowns
hold.unknowns <- all.papers[which(all.papers$Plant.age.at.infestation..days=="Unknown"),]
all.papers.plant <- all.papers[-which(all.papers$Plant.age.at.infestation..days=="Unknown"),]
hold.unknowns$AAI_binned <- "Unknown"
all.papers.plant <- all.papers.plant %>% mutate(AAI_binned = cut(as.numeric(Plant.age.at.infestation..days),
                                                                breaks = 4)) %>%
  rbind(hold.unknowns)

#plot
plant.mosaic <- all.papers.plant %>% group_by(PlFuGu, AAI_binned) %>%
  summarise(count = n()) %>%
  mutate(cut.count = sum(count),
         prop = count/sum(count)) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = PlFuGu, y = prop, width = cut.count, fill = AAI_binned)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", position = "fill", colour = "black") +
  geom_text(aes(label = paste("(", count, ")", sep = "")),
            position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5)) + # if labels are desired
  facet_grid(~PlFuGu, scales = "free_x", space = "free_x") +
  scale_fill_manual(labels = c("10-34 days", "35-59 days", "60-84 days",
                              "85-110 days", "Unknown"),
                   values = setColors("#984d7479", 5)) +
```

```

theme_classic() +
theme(strip.background = element_blank(),
      strip.text = element_blank(),
      axis.text.y = element_blank(), axis.title.y = element_blank(),
      axis.ticks.y = element_blank(), axis.line.y = element_blank(),
      text = element_text(size = 18)) +
labs(fill = "Age at infestation", x = "Plant domestication status")

```

'summarise()' has grouped output by 'PlFuGu'. You can override using the ## '.groups' argument.

```
plant.mosaic
```



```

###microbe
#aesthetic changes and making soil diversity a factor so that it can be organized more logically
all.papers[all.papers$MiFuGu=="Endophytic entomopathogen",]$MiFuGu <- "Other GPPF"
all.papers[all.papers$MiFuGu=="PGPB",]$MiFuGu <- "Other PGPB"
all.papers$CoCoSimple_f <- factor(all.papers$CoCoSimple,
                                levels = c("Complex", "Small consortia", "Single", "Unknown"))
all.papers[all.papers$MiFuGu=="N-fixing",]$MiFuGu <- "N-fixing bacteria"

microbe.mosaic <- all.papers %>% group_by(CoCoSimple_f, MiFuGu) %>%
  summarise(count = n()) %>%
  mutate(cut.count = sum(count),

```

```

    prop = count/sum(count)) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = CoCoSimple_f, y = prop, width = cut.count, fill = MiFuGu)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", position = "fill", colour = "black") +
  geom_text(aes(label = paste("(", count, ")", sep = "")),
            position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5)) + # if labels are desired
  facet_grid(~CoCoSimple_f, scales = "free_x", space = "free_x") +
  scale_x_discrete(labels = label_wrap(8)) +
  scale_fill_manual(values = setColors("#984d7479", 6)) +
  theme_classic() +
  theme(strip.background = element_blank(),
        strip.text = element_blank(),
        axis.text.y = element_blank(), axis.title.y = element_blank(),
        axis.ticks.y = element_blank(), axis.line.y = element_blank(),
        text = element_text(size = 18)) +
  labs(fill = str_wrap("Microbial inoculant functional guild", 20), x = "Total soil community diversity

```

'summarise()' has grouped output by 'CoCoSimple_f'. You can override using the ## '.groups' argument.

microbe.mosaic


```

###environmental/experimental
#bin the regrowth-period-duration variable; once again first remove unknowns, then bin, then rbind unkn

```

```

hold.unknowns <- all.papers[all.papers$RP.duration..days.=="Unknown",]
all.papers2 <- all.papers[~which(all.papers$RP.duration..days.=="Unknown"),]
hold.unknowns$RPD_binned <- "Unknown"
all.papers.RPD <- all.papers2 %>% mutate(RPD_binned = cut(as.numeric(RP.duration..days.),
                                                    breaks = c(-1,1,25,50,75, 100))) #set 0's apart
all.papers.RPD <- rbind(all.papers.RPD, hold.unknowns)
all.papers.RPD$Environ[all.papers.RPD$Environ == "Field" | all.papers.RPD$Environ == "Agricultural field"]

exp.mosaic <- all.papers.RPD %>% group_by(Environ, RPD_binned) %>%
  summarise(count = n()) %>%
  mutate(cut.count = sum(count),
         prop = count/sum(count)) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = Environ, y = prop, width = cut.count, fill = RPD_binned)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", position = "fill", colour = "black") +
  geom_text(aes(label = paste("(", count, ")", sep = "")),
           position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5)) + # if labels are desired
  facet_grid(~Environ, scales = "free_x", space = "free_x") +
  scale_x_discrete(labels = label_wrap(8)) +
  scale_fill_manual(values = setColors("#984d7479", 6),
                   labels = c("0 days", "1-25 days",
                              "26-50 days", "51-75 days",
                              "76-100 days", "Unknown")) +
  theme_classic() +
  theme(strip.background = element_blank(),
        strip.text = element_blank(),
        axis.text.y = element_blank(), axis.title.y = element_blank(),
        axis.ticks.y = element_blank(), axis.line.y = element_blank(),
        text = element_text(size = 18)) +
  labs(fill = "Regrowth period", x = "Experimental environment")

```

'summarise()' has grouped output by 'Environ'. You can override using the
'.groups' argument.

```
exp.mosaic
```



```
#setwd("/Users/emilytronson/OneDrive - purdue.edu/Tronson Meeting Files/Literature Review")
#ggsave("insect-mosaic.pdf", insect.mosaic, height = 7, width = 9)
#ggsave("microbe-mosaic.pdf", microbe.mosaic, height = 7, width = 9)
#ggsave("plant-mosaic.pdf", plant.mosaic, height = 7, width = 9)
#ggsave("exp-mosaic.pdf", exp.mosaic, height = 7, width = 9)
```

```
insect.mosaic <- all.papers %>% group_by(InFit, RoShHe) %>%
  summarise(count = n()) %>%
  mutate(cut.count = sum(count),
         prop = count/sum(count)) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = InFit, y = prop, width = cut.count, fill = RoShHe)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", position = "fill", colour = "black") +
  geom_text(aes(label = paste("(", count, ")", sep = "")),
           position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5)) + # if labels are desired
  facet_grid(~InFit, scales = "free_x", space = "free_x") +
  scale_fill_manual(values = tetradic("#984d7479")) +
  theme_classic() +
  theme(strip.background = element_blank(),
        strip.text = element_blank(),
        axis.text.y = element_blank(), axis.title.y = element_blank(),
        axis.ticks.y = element_blank(), axis.line.y = element_blank(),
        text = element_text(size = 18))+
  labs(fill = "Site of herbivore feeding", x = "Insect fitness")
```

'summarise()' has grouped output by 'InFit'. You can override using the

'.groups' argument.

Tetradic colors of: #984D7479

`insect.mosaic`


```

###microbe
#aesthetic changes and making soil diversity a factor so that it can be organized more logically
all.papers[all.papers$MiSource=="Lab stock",]$MiSource <- "Academic stock"
all.papers$CoCoSimple_f <- factor(all.papers$CoCoSimple,
                                levels = c("Complex", "Small consortia", "Single", "Unknown"))

all.papers %>% group_by(CoCoSimple_f, MiSource) %>%
  summarise(count = n()) %>%
  mutate(cut.count = sum(count),
         prop = count/sum(count)) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = CoCoSimple_f, y = prop, width = cut.count, fill = MiSource)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", position = "fill", colour = "black") +
  geom_text(aes(label = paste("(", count, ")", sep = "")),
           position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5)) + # if labels are desired
  facet_grid(~CoCoSimple_f, scales = "free_x", space = "free_x") +
  scale_x_discrete(labels = label_wrap(8)) +
  scale_fill_manual(values = setColors("#984d7479", 6)) +
  theme_classic() +
  theme(strip.background = element_blank(),
        strip.text = element_blank(),
        axis.text.y = element_blank(), axis.title.y = element_blank(),
        axis.ticks.y = element_blank(), axis.line.y = element_blank(),
        text = element_text(size = 18)) +
  labs(fill = str_wrap("Microbe source", 20), x = "Total soil community diversity")

```

```
## 'summarise()' has grouped output by 'CoCoSimple_f'. You can override using the
## '.groups' argument.
```



```
#bin age-at-infestation data; we first need to remove the "Unknowns," then bin, then rbind the Unknowns
hold.unknowns <- all.papers[which(all.papers$Plant.age.at.infestation..days=="Unknown"),]
all.papers.plant <- all.papers[-which(all.papers$Plant.age.at.infestation..days=="Unknown"),]
all.papers.plant %>% group_by(PIFuGu) %>% summarise(mean = mean(as.numeric(Plant.age.at.infestation..days)))
```

```
## # A tibble: 2 x 2
##   PIFuGu      mean
##   <chr>      <dbl>
## 1 Cultivated  37.2
## 2 Uncultivated 68.5
```

```
hold.unknowns$AAI_binned <- "Unknown"
all.papers.plant <- all.papers.plant %>% mutate(AAI_binned = cut(as.numeric(Plant.age.at.infestation..days),
                                                                breaks = 4)) %>%
  rbind(hold.unknowns)

#plot
plant.mosaic <- all.papers.plant %>% group_by(PIFuGu, AAI_binned) %>%
  summarise(count = n()) %>%
  mutate(cut.count = sum(count),
         prop = count/sum(count)) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
```

```

ggplot(aes(x = PlFuGu, y = prop, width = cut.count, fill = AAI_binned)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", position = "fill", colour = "black") +
  geom_text(aes(label = paste("(", count, ")"), sep = "")),
  position = position_stack(vjust = 0.5)) + # if labels are desired
facet_grid(~PlFuGu, scales = "free_x", space = "free_x") +
scale_fill_manual(labels = c("10-34 days", "35-59 days", "60-84 days",
                             "85-110 days", "Unknown"),
                  values = setColors("#984d7479", 5)) +
theme_classic() +
theme(strip.background = element_blank(),
      strip.text = element_blank(),
      axis.text.y = element_blank(), axis.title.y = element_blank(),
      axis.ticks.y = element_blank(), axis.line.y = element_blank(),
      text = element_text(size = 18)) +
labs(fill = "Age at infestation", x = "Plant domestication status")

```

```

## 'summarise()' has grouped output by 'PlFuGu'. You can override using the
## '.groups' argument.

```

```
plant.mosaic
```



```
toltab %>% group_by(Citation) %>% summarise(nrow = n())
```

```
## # A tibble: 40 x 2
```

```
## Citation nrow
## <chr> <int>
## 1 Balog et al. 2017 6
## 2 Batool et al. 2022 6
## 3 Bennett and Bever 2007 4
## 4 Bernaola and Stout 2019 4
## 5 Bernaola and Stout 2021 4
## 6 Borowicz 1997 1
## 7 Borowicz 2009 1
## 8 Brunner et al. 2014 6
## 9 Caccavo et al. 2022 1
## 10 Charters et al. 2022 3
## # i 30 more rows
```

```
es.agg %>% group_by(Citation) %>% summarise(nrow = n())
```

```
## # A tibble: 35 x 2
## Citation nrow
## <chr> <int>
## 1 Balog et al. 2017 4
## 2 Batool et al. 2022 6
## 3 Bennett and Bever 2007 3
## 4 Bernaola and Stout 2019 4
## 5 Bernaola and Stout 2021 4
## 6 Borowicz 2009 1
## 7 Brunner et al. 2014 3
## 8 Caccavo et al. 2022 1
## 9 Charters et al. 2022 3
## 10 Chen et al. 2021 1
## # i 25 more rows
```